

NATAE
North African Transition
to AgroEcology

D6.1 Report of the Regional Conference on Agroecology: Science and Policy

January 29 – 31, 2025
(Regency Hotel, Gammarth, Tunisia)

www.natae-agroecology.eu

Funded by
the European Union

This project is funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement no. 101084647. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. For the associated partner in the NATAE project, this work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Project funded by

 Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Document Control Sheet

Project Number	
Project Acronym	NATAE
Project Full title	Fostering agroecology transition in North Africa through multi-actor, evaluation, and networking
Project Start Date	1 December 2022
Project Duration	48 months
Funding Instrument	Horizon Europe Funding Scheme Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01
Coordinator	Mélanie Requier-Desjardins (requier@iamm.fr), CIHEAM-IAMM, UMR SENS, Montpellier

Deliverable Information

Document No	Milestone 6
Document Title	Report of the Regional Conference on Agroecology: Science and Policy
Work-Package No	6
Work-Package Title	EU-compliant policies to foster AE transition in North African countries
WP-Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	ZALF
Task No	N/A
Task Title	Holding a mid-term policy conference
Task Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	Ndeye Fatou MAR (OSS)
Main Author (Name and Short Org. Name)	Ndeye Fatou MAR (OSS)
Other Authors (Name and Short Org. Name)	Mélanie Requier, Rita Jalkh (CIHEAM-IAMM)
Status	Final <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Deliverable Type	Report <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Data <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/>
Dissemination Level	Public (PU) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sensitive (SEN) <input type="checkbox"/> Classified <input type="checkbox"/> PU: Public, fully open SEN: Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444 Classified C-EU/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444 Classified S-EU/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444
Date Approved by Coordinator	17 February 2025

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Executive Summary

Under the high patronage of the Minister of Environment of Tunisia, the Sahara and Sahel Observatory (OSS), in partnership with the Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Montpellier (CIHEAM-IAMM), organized, from January 29 to 31, 2025 in Tunis, a high-level regional conference entitled "**Agroecology: Science and Policy**". This event brought together more than 150 participants in person and nearly 200 registered online, testifying to the growing mobilization of regional actors around the crucial issues related to agroecology.

The central objective of this first policy conference of the NATAE project is to accelerate the agroecological transition for resilient food systems in North Africa by promoting agroecology as a strategic lever in the face of the environmental and food challenges of the region.

North Africa faces increasingly pressing challenges, including land degradation, water scarcity and the impacts of climate change, all of which threaten food security and the sustainability of agricultural systems. In this context, agroecology presents itself as a viable alternative, combining traditional knowledge and scientific advances to establish resilient agricultural practices, reduce the environmental footprint and preserve natural resources.

This conference was a multi-stakeholder platform for strategic exchange where policy makers, researchers and teachers, experts, students, farmers, representatives of international organizations and civil society actors debated the integration of agroecological principles into public policies and agricultural practices in the region. The event thus made it possible to identify concrete courses of action and to strengthen the dynamics of cooperation in favor of an agroecological transition adapted to local realities.

An opening under the sign of scientific and political cooperation

The opening ceremony was marked by the interventions of leading personalities, reflecting the collective commitment to sustainable agricultural development. Mr. Nabil Ben Khatra, Executive Secretary of the OSS, insisted on the importance of regional cooperation and scientific mobilization for an inclusive and effective agroecological transition. H.E. Mr Giuseppe Perrone, Ambassador of the European Union to Tunisia, underlined the central role of European support in promoting sustainable agricultural practices that reconcile productivity and the preservation of natural resources.

For his part, H.E. Mr. Bassem Yahia Hassan, Ambassador of the Arab Republic of Egypt, whose message was relayed by Mr. Samy Abo Ragab, representative of the Desert Research Center, highlighted the Egyptian experience in agroecological innovation and adaptation to climate constraints. Mrs. Elen Lemaitre-Curri, Deputy Director of the CIHEAM-IAMM, insisted on the need to decompartmentalize knowledge and to articulate scientific advances with ancestral agroecological know-how to optimize their implementation at the local and regional levels.

In his opening remarks, H.E. Mr. Habib Abid, Minister of Environment of Tunisia, recalled that agroecology is not limited to a technical approach, but is an integrated framework that respects the environmental, economic and social dimensions of agricultural development. He underlined its fundamental role in preserving natural resources, combating land degradation and promoting green jobs, all strategic levers for inclusive and sustainable agricultural development in North Africa.

An unprecedented political and multi-stakeholder mobilization

The event brought together a wide range of institutional and diplomatic actors, with the participation of current ministers, former ministers, ambassadors and senior officials of national and international institutions. The diversity of the speakers and participants fostered a rich exchange of perspectives and made it possible to identify concrete levers to accelerate the agroecological transition. The debates highlighted several priority areas, including the importance of an intersectoral approach involving the environment, agriculture, water and health sectors, as well as the need for a structuring and coherent policy and regulatory framework to effectively support this transition.

The key role of research and training was also highlighted as an essential driver for a better appropriation and dissemination of agroecological practices. The networking of actors and the sharing of experiences have contributed to strengthening the collective dynamic in favor of a paradigm shift in North African agricultural systems.

A space for exchange, networking and promotion of research results

Beyond technical and policy discussions, the conference offered a platform for the exchange of experiences and good practices, highlighting innovative agroecological initiatives adapted to local specificities. The interactions between the various actors have fostered the development of new strategic synergies and the strengthening of regional collaborations to support the agroecological transition.

A refined understanding of agroecology in North Africa

Agroecology is no longer considered as a simple return to ancestral agricultural practices, it is on the contrary a set of innovations and transformations, which can be inspired, totally or partially, by traditional know-how and local, often non-academic, knowledge. It is thus a question of hybrid knowledge, sometimes combining technological advances, but also of co-creation and sharing of information between various actors and communities. Agroecology is therefore based on a dynamic of exchange and adaptation, integrating evolving needs in terms of innovation, equipment, technical itineraries and knowledge.

Agroecology stands out above all for its fundamental role in preventing land degradation, thus ensuring the long-term sustainability of agricultural systems. It is based on the rational management of natural resources, an essential dimension that is not only widely recognized, but also demonstrated both scientifically and empirically.

It is productive by respecting biophysical mechanisms and protecting natural resources, whether it is fauna, flora, soil fertility, water preservation or climate regulation at the micro and macro scales. Although its yields do not always compete with those of intensified agricultural models, it nevertheless ensures more stable production over the years, thus limiting losses during extreme climatic periods. In addition, it guarantees superior nutritional quality, contributing to public health in a context marked by the resurgence of diseases linked to dietary changes in the region: overconsumption of fats and sugars, increase in cases of diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, etc.

However, countries in the region are facing increasingly pressing food constraints, which can push actors to favor solutions that are accessible in the short term, sometimes to the detriment of an agroecological transition that is nevertheless resilient and sustainable.

These opportunities and this context require renewed public policy action in favor of agroecology in the region.

Strategic recommendations for a successful transition

The work of the conference led to several strategic axes to accelerate the adoption of agroecology in North Africa. It was recommended that an integrated and contextualized approach, combining scientific results and traditional knowledge, should be promoted, while at the same time providing policy and regulatory incentives. The development of innovative financing mechanisms, such as dedicated funds and economic incentives, was also identified as a crucial lever.

Strengthening the capacities of stakeholders, in particular through adapted training for farmers, technicians and researchers, as well as improving access to markets through quality labels and more structured marketing channels, are among the priorities defined. Finally, the establishment of monitoring and evaluation mechanisms and the promotion of regional cooperation appear to be essential elements to guarantee the success of this agroecological transition.

In his closing remarks, Mr. Nabil Ben Khatra recalled that agroecology is no longer a simple alternative, but an unavoidable necessity to strengthen the resilience of food systems in the face of environmental and climate crises.

Sustainable impact to strengthen agroecological research and policies

The conference marks a turning point in the promotion of agroecology in North Africa. The scale of the mobilization and the commitment of the participants testify to a strong dynamic in favor of a structural transformation of food systems.

The OSS and its partners are committed to ensuring rigorous follow-up on the commitments made at this conference, so that the recommendations made are translated into concrete and sustainable actions for the benefit of the people and ecosystems of the region.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

Agriculture is at the heart of North Africa's food systems and environmental challenges. This arid and semi-arid region is subject to marked climatic constraints, with rising temperatures, increased rainfall variability and longer periods of drought. These conditions directly affect agricultural productivity and increase the vulnerability of rural populations who depend heavily on agriculture for their livelihoods.

Faced with soil degradation, water scarcity and the growing effects of climate change, traditional agricultural models are struggling to ensure sustainable and resilient production. Conventional agriculture, which focuses on the intensive use of chemical inputs and unsustainable irrigation techniques, contributes to the depletion of natural resources and the impoverishment of soils.

Agroecology presents itself as a viable and necessary alternative, integrating both modern scientific approaches and traditional knowledge to ensure the sustainability of agricultural systems. It is based on ecological principles aimed at restoring the natural balance of agricultural ecosystems, while improving the productivity and resilience of farms. It encourages crop diversification, the reduction of the use of chemical inputs, the development of short circuits and the involvement of local communities in the management of natural resources.

North Africa is a region facing multiple challenges that threaten food security and agricultural ecosystems. Among these challenges, pressure on natural resources, declining soil fertility and the impacts of climate change directly affect agricultural productivity and the resilience of food systems. Smallholders, who make up a large part of the agricultural sector in the region, are particularly vulnerable to climate and economic shocks. They need appropriate solutions to ensure their food security and improve their living conditions.

The adoption of more sustainable and resilient agricultural models has become a priority to ensure a secure food future for the people of the region. In this context, it is essential to strengthen farmers' capacities, promote public policies that promote agroecological practices and put in place economic incentives to support this transition.

In this context, the Sahara and Sahel Observatory (OSS), in partnership with the Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Montpellier (CIHEAM-IAMM), organized from January 29 to 31, 2025 in Tunis a high-level regional conference entitled "Agroecology: Science and Policy". This event, held under the patronage of the Minister of Environment of Tunisia, brought together more than 150 participants in person and nearly 200 registered online, thus illustrating the importance given to this agroecological transition.

Chapter 2

Conducting the conference

2. Conducting the conference

2.1 Official opening

Bringing together a wide range of key stakeholders, including policymakers, representatives of public administrations in charge of agricultural and environmental sectoral policies, experts and former ministers, researchers, teachers, farmers and representatives of civil society organisations and the banking sector, this event has established itself as a multi-stakeholder platform for dialogue and exchange essential for the promotion of agroecology as a strategic response to environmental, climate and food security challenges in North Africa. By focusing on synergies between science, public policies and sustainable agricultural practices, this meeting aimed to catalyze an agroecological transition adapted to the specificities of the region's ecosystems and societies and to ensure increased resilience to climate shocks.

The opening ceremony was chaired by the Minister of Environment of Tunisia, Mr. Habib Abid. It was notable for high-level interventions, illustrating the commitment of stakeholders to this innovative approach. Mr. Nabil Ben Khadra, Executive Secretary of the OSS, highlighted the fundamental role of regional cooperation and scientific research to support an inclusive and effective agroecological transition. Mr. Giuseppe Perrone, Ambassador of the European Union to Tunisia, underlined the importance of European support for initiatives promoting sustainable and resilient agriculture, capable of reconciling productivity and the preservation of natural resources.

For his part, Mr. Bassem Yahia Hassan, Ambassador of the Arab Republic of Egypt, whose message was conveyed by Mr. Samy Abo Ragab, representative of the Desert Research Center, highlighted Egypt's experience in adapting to climate constraints and agroecological innovation. Mrs. Elen Lemaitre-Curri, Deputy Director of the CIHEAM-IAMM, insisted on the need to decompartmentalize knowledge and to combine scientific advances with ancestral agroecological practices in order to optimize their implementation at the local and regional levels.

The opening speech of the Minister of Environment of Tunisia recalled that agroecology is not only a technical alternative, but a holistic approach integrating the environmental, economic and social dimensions of agricultural development. His Excellency Mr. Habib Abid highlighted his role in the preservation of natural resources, the restoration of degraded soils, the fight against climate change and the promotion of green jobs, all strategic levers for inclusive and sustainable agricultural development in North Africa.

Photo 1: Opening Ceremony: from left to right, the EU Ambassador, His Excellency, Mr. The Minister of Environment in Tunisia, Mr. E. S. of the OSS, organizer of the event and Mrs. the Deputy Director of the CIHEAM-IAMM, co-organizer of the event

2.2 Launch of the conference

Presentation of the agenda and objectives of the conference

The conference began with a presentation of the agenda and strategic objectives of the conference, placed within the framework of the specific objectives of the Horizon Europe NATAE project in which this conference falls under. In a presentation moderated by **Mrs. Mélanie Requier Desjardins (CIHEAM-IAMM, scientific coordinator of the NATAE project)**, she highlighted the need to accelerate the agroecological transition in North Africa in the face of the growing challenges of climate change, soil degradation and the scarcity of natural resources. In this context, she detailed three priority areas for the work of this conference:

1. **To provide key elements to public decision-makers** to influence agricultural policies, education and training, by integrating agroecological approaches adapted to local contexts.
2. **Broaden the issue of production** to the entire value chain to promote the emergence of markets dedicated to agroecological products and support viable economic models.
3. **To support the setting up of a multi-stakeholder Mediterranean network, the MEDAE network**, in order to structure and federate the various agroecological initiatives at the regional level.
4. **Rely on multi-stakeholder dialogue to move forward** on these three priority areas, taking advantage of the richness of the audience present in the room and remotely, for this event.

She also mentioned how the NATAE project is also based on a multi-stakeholder approach, and that it is relying on 7 main sites work in progress, carefully selected to reflect the diversity of the agroecosystems of the region and serve as platforms for innovation and experimentation in agroecology. She insisted on the necessity to consider agroecology as a systemic concept encompassing multiple dimensions, from biophysical to economic, social and political dimension.

Finally, she added that the work of this first conference will feed into the organization of the second political conference of the NATAE project scheduled to take place in Montpellier in September-October 2026.

Overview of agroecology in the NATAE region as a climate change hotspot

The intervention of **Prof. Rachel Bezner Kerr (Cornell University and member of the NATAE Advisory Board)** broadened the reflection on the climate and agricultural challenges affecting North Africa and the Mediterranean region. In her presentation, Prof. Bezner Kerr pointed out that this region is a real "**hot spot**" of **climate change**, characterized by accentuated warming phenomena, intensifying droughts and accelerated soil degradation. These effects combine to put increasing pressure on natural resources, including water and arable land, which are already subject to intensive exploitation.

Prof. Bezner Kerr detailed several worrying trends:

- **Intensifying droughts:** Increasing water scarcity, which is essential for agriculture, is exacerbating the challenges for rural communities that depend on irrigation for their crops.
- **Rising temperatures:** Continued increases in temperatures contribute to desertification and disrupt agricultural production cycles, leading to yield losses and increased food insecurity.
- **Land degradation:** Erosion and depletion of fertile land compromise the ability of ecosystems to support sustainable agriculture.

Faced with these challenges, Prof. Bezner Kerr highlighted **agroecology** as a systemic and resilient solution. It has demonstrated, based on international research and case studies and real-world assessments, that agroecological practices—integrating traditional knowledge with modern scientific approaches—can both improve agricultural productivity and preserve natural ecosystems. Among these practices, she cited agroforestry, crop diversification and integrated water resources management, which offer real opportunities to mitigate the negative impacts of climate change.

Prof. Bezner Kerr also stressed the importance of an integrated and collaborative approach. She called for a strong involvement of local actors, including farmers, researchers, policymakers and civil society organizations, to co-construct solutions tailored to the specific contexts of each region. Democratic and participatory governance, supported by substantial investments in research and experimentation, is essential to transform these challenges into opportunities for sustainable development. Finally, she stressed the important role of women in reasoning the choice of productive strategies to increase the food security of agricultural households and the preservation of natural resources.

In conclusion, Prof. Bezner Kerr recalled the urgency of taking action on these major climate issues. The Mediterranean region and North Africa, as particularly vulnerable areas, require a coordinated response that integrates environmental, social and economic dimensions. Only a synergy between local initiatives, appropriate public policies and institutional support will make it possible to preserve natural resources and guarantee sustainable food security for future generations.

This opening session laid the foundations for the discussions that followed, highlighting the need for strengthened collaboration and concrete actions to make agroecology a viable and sustainable alternative to the socio-environmental challenges of the region.

Link to the presentations can be found [HERE](#).

2.3 Agroecology in action: Perspectives from the MEDAE network

The MEDAE network

The **MEDAE (Mediterranean multi-actor network on agroecology)** network is an initiative to promote the agroecological transition in North Africa. Faced with the growing challenges of climate change, soil degradation and water scarcity, this network seeks to structure and federate the actors committed to sustainable and resilient agricultural practices.

Agroecology appears to be a response adapted to the specificities of the region, by promoting local knowledge and scientific innovations. MEDAE emphasizes a collaborative approach involving public institutions, researchers, farmers, civil society organizations and the private sector to build a more resilient and sustainable agriculture.

This session was moderated by **Mr. Mounir Majdoub**, who presented the major challenges facing North Africa. He highlighted water scarcity, land degradation and the impacts of climate change, highlighting the increasing pressure on agricultural and food systems. He insisted on the need to develop an agroecology adapted to these challenges, combining traditional practices and scientific innovations.

Ms Mélanie Requier-Desjardins then detailed the prospects of the MEDAE network. She explained in the presentation of the network prepared by Marion Comptour (CARI) in charge of this activity within the NATAE project, that this network is a multi-stakeholder network, composed of organizations and not individuals, representing various disciplines and statuses. Its collaborative model aims to create synergies and strengthen local and regional actions for an effective agroecological transition.

Among the specific objectives of the MEDAE network, the presentation highlighted:

- Stimulate exchanges and collaborations between professionals involved in the agroecological transition.
- Promote training sessions and webinars to share knowledge and successful experiences.
- Create materials to influence public policies in favour of agroecology.

These actions aim to make MEDAE a strategic lever for the development of more sustainable and resilient agricultural systems in North Africa.

Summary of Discussions and Highlights

The session continued with a panel of exchanges and sharing of experiences, bringing together experts representing different scales of intervention: local, African and Mediterranean. This panel highlighted innovative initiatives and approaches adapted to the challenges of agroecology in various contexts.

1. The local experience of the ACDD (Association for Conservation and Sustainable Development in Tunisia)

Mr. Abdelbacet Hamrouni, representative of the ACDD, presented a Tunisian local initiative focused on community-based management of natural resources in oases. This initiative, with more than 20 years of experience, demonstrates how local governance and the active participation of farmers allow for better adaptation to climate change. The actions put in place include sustainable water management, crop diversification and the introduction of traditional agroecological techniques.

2. The African experience of PAFO (Pan-African Farmers' Organization, Rwanda)

Mr. Aimable Twagirayezu, representative of PAFO shared the African experience in agroecology and resilience to extreme climatic conditions. This initiative illustrates how agroecology is applied on a continental scale, through regenerative agricultural practices and integrated food systems. The exchange of know-how between African countries plays a key role in the dissemination of good agroecological practices.

3. The Mediterranean Experience, Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem Approach (WEFE Nexus, Union for the Mediterranean, Cyprus)

Mr. Frédéric Dinechin, specialist of the Nexus WEFE, Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem put forward an integrated approach to natural resource management for sustainable agriculture. This approach, implemented within the Union for the Mediterranean, promotes an optimization of the interactions between water, energy, food and ecosystems, while minimizing negative impacts on the environment. Pilot experiences carried out in the framework of the WEFE Nexus have demonstrated the importance of coordinated public policy planning to ensure sustainable resource management.

Key messages

- **The urgency of an agroecological transition:** In the face of climate change, the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices is essential to ensure food security and preserve biodiversity.
- **The strategic role of the MEDAE network:** It aims to promote exchanges between actors, structure local initiatives and influence public policies in favour of agroecology.
- **Lessons learned from the case of Tunisian oases:** The experience of the ACDD demonstrates the importance of rational management of resources (water, soil, biodiversity) and the need for better development of agricultural products.
- **The Nexus WEFE approach as an integrated solution:** The joint management of water, energy and agriculture allows for better resilience in the face of environmental and economic crises.
- **The pan-African experience of PAFO:** Africa as a whole, shares similar challenges, and the pooling of resilience strategies allows for better overall adaptation to climate change.

Key recommendations

- **Strengthen public policies in favour of agroecology** by integrating incentives and appropriate financing.
- **Develop pilot initiatives and exchange platforms** to test and disseminate good agroecological practices.
- **Increase training and awareness** among farmers, youth and policymakers to encourage the adoption of sustainable practices.
- **Support research and innovation** on agroecological solutions adapted to the specificities of North Africa.
- **Encourage a territorial and inclusive approach** by involving all local actors in the governance of natural resources.
- **Promote the WEFE Nexus in agricultural policies** to ensure more efficient resource management and better coordination across sectors.
- **Promote the networking of local and African initiatives** to capitalize on experiences and encourage regional cooperation.

Link to the presentations can be found [HERE](#).

2.4 Side event: Green Corridor

On the sidelines of this Conference, a side event was dedicated to the "**Green Corridor in Tunisia**" initiative, organized by the Ministry of Environment in partnership with the Sahara and Sahel Observatory (OSS). This strategic project aims to restore 260,000 hectares of degraded land in the country's driest regions, strengthen ecosystem resilience, create green jobs and improve the living conditions of local populations, while combating the effects of climate change. Launched by **Mr. Hédi CHEBILI, Director General of Environment and Quality of Life**, and **Mr. Nabil BEN KHATRA, Executive Secretary of the OSS**, this event brought together political decision-makers, technical and financial partners, institutional representatives, the private sector and civil society to exchange on past experiences in green belts and dams, and identify challenges related to land restoration and explore funding opportunities. As part of the **NATAE** programme, which works for the agroecological transition in North Africa, the Green Corridor is based on five major axes:

- Land restoration and sustainable ecosystem management,
- Strengthening agricultural resilience to climate change,
- The consolidation of local production chains,
- Optimization of economic and institutional frameworks for effective governance,
- Strengthening local capacities through training and dissemination of good practices.

The discussions highlighted innovative approaches and concrete solutions for the sustainable management of natural resources, stressing the urgency of mobilizing technical and financial support to ensure the success of this initiative. By combining traditional practices and agroecological innovations, the Green Corridor is positioned as a strategic response to Tunisia's environmental and socio-economic challenges, illustrating a desire to adopt a sustainable, integrated and inclusive approach for the future of the country's agriculture and ecosystems.

Link to the presentation can be found [HERE](#).

Photo 2: Mr. The Director General of the Environment and Quality of Life and Mr. OSS Executive Secretary presents the Green Corridor initiative

2.5 High-Level Roundtable: Policy and Public Education Strategies to Accelerate the Agroecological Transition and Promotion Strategies at All Levels

Summary of Discussions and Highlights

This high-level roundtable provided a crucial opportunity to start a constructive dialogue on the challenges and opportunities of agroecology in North Africa. Emphasis was placed on the strategies needed to accelerate the agroecological transition, in particular through the development of targeted public policies and promotional actions adapted to each level of governance. This exchange made it possible to introduce the main issues related to agroecology and to lay the foundations of a collaborative dynamic, while highlighting the essential dimensions for the success of this transition.

A region under pressure: between vulnerability and the need for change

Mr. Patrice Burger, President of CARI, gave a worrying assessment: the Mediterranean is one of the most vulnerable regions to global warming, with temperatures expected to rise by 2 to 3°C by 2040. Already marked by great water scarcity, the region is facing accelerated desertification and a significant decrease in agricultural yields, which could fall by another 50% in North Africa in the coming decades.

Faced with this emergency, public policies are struggling to support the transition to more resilient agricultural systems. Conventional agriculture is revealing its limits: stagnant yields, high environmental and social costs. Globally, the negative externalities of food systems are estimated at \$12 trillion per year, making a paradigm shift imperative.

Agroecology: between traditions and innovations

Agroecology, based on traditional knowledge and structured as a systems approach, combines agronomic performance, social resilience and economic viability. Several international experiences testify to the effectiveness of this approach. In India, particularly in Uttar Pradesh, the agroecological transition has been successful. In Sri Lanka, on the other hand, poorly calibrated policy adjustments have hampered its implementation. In addition, institutions such as IPBES, FAO and HLPE are working to harmonize definitions and methodologies to facilitate their adoption at different scales.

However, obstacles remain:

- **Biased performance evaluation:** agroecological systems are often judged solely on unit yield, an indicator that is unsuitable in the face of current climate challenges.
- **Criteria to be rethought:** more comprehensive indicators are needed, taking into account resilience, biodiversity and co-benefits (e.g., FAO's TAP, GTAE, Biovision tools).
- **Political and economic resistance:** despite solid scientific evidence, the agroecological transition is still struggling to convince some decision-makers and dominant players in the sector.

Debates and perspectives: removing the obstacles, demonstrating effectiveness

Mr. Elyes Hamza, Director of RAC/SPA and former Minister of Agriculture in Tunisia, stressed that sustainability is a fundamental pillar of agriculture: without sustainability, no system can thrive in the long term. He insisted on the integration of local knowledge to design modern and adapted

solutions. Far from being a step backwards, agroecology is a contemporary response to environmental and social challenges.

Mr. Assane Soumare, former Minister, Mauritania, highlighted two major obstacles: the lack of political commitment and a society disconnected from its agricultural land, favouring imported models. The reconnection of communities with their territory is a crucial issue.

Mr. Thierry Dupeuble, Director of the IAMM in France, pleaded for a change in the criteria for evaluating agricultural performance stating that yield per plot can no longer be the only reference in a world where climatic hazards redefine each season.

Mr. Bruno Romagny, Research Director, IRD and member of the NATAE Advisory Board, supported this position, stressing that although technical and economic arguments exist, political and economic barriers still hinder their adoption. The evaluation **of the co-benefits** of agroecology, in particular through analyses such as those of the Economics of Land Degradation, could be a decisive lever for convincing decision-makers.

Ms. Laura Tabet, Director of Nawaya, Egypt, stressed the importance of **co-creation of knowledge**. While agroecological innovations exist, their dissemination and local adaptation remain essential. Tools such as validated science videos allow for rapid and effective transmission of good practices between farmers and their peer-to-peer discussions throughout the region, and probably beyond.

Mr. Said Amri, Director of ENAM in Morocco, stressed the urgency of strengthening training in agroecology. He also referred to a global coalition of 50 states that is working to structure this transition, noting that Mauritania and Morocco are currently the only representatives of North Africa. He insisted on the importance of their commitment to integrate agroecology at the heart of regional agricultural strategies, a key element in accelerating this transition in the region.

Key messages

The Agroecological Transition: A Necessity, not a Trend

Far from being a passing trend, the agroecological transition is an essential response to environmental, economic and social challenges. **This is not a step backwards, but a smart modernization of agricultural practices**, combining traditional knowledge and innovations adapted to local realities. This change must be **gradual, inclusive and structured to avoid any sudden break**.

From Traditional Techniques to Agroecology: An Evolution, Not an Idealization

Ancestral agricultural practices are **a valuable basis, but they should not be set in stone**. Agroecology is based on their re-evaluation and enrichment through innovative approaches, integrating ecological dynamics and scientific advances to ensure their effectiveness and sustainability.

Dispelling Preconceived Ideas: An Imperative for the Credibility of Agroecology

The agroecological transition still suffers from preconceived ideas that hinder its adoption. The establishment of **Bureaux de Verification des Idées Reçues (BVIR)** would make it possible to confront these perceptions with the realities on the ground, to provide concrete evidence of the viability of agroecology and to explore innovative financing mechanisms such as carbon finance.

Public Procurement: A Decisive Lever for Transforming Agriculture

Public procurement can accelerate the transition by directing their purchases towards agroecological products (school canteens, hospitals, etc.). This strategy would not only ensure sustainable demand, but also encourage a growing number of producers to adopt more environmentally friendly practices.

An International Synergy to Strengthen the Recognition of Agroecology

Integration into global coalitions is essential to ensure that agroecological principles are recognized and valued. A collective international commitment would provide new opportunities for farmers and facilitate the opening of fairer markets.

A Transition That Goes Beyond the Technical Framework: A Global Societal Challenge

The agroecological transition is not just a technical transformation of agricultural practices. It touches on social, economic and environmental dimensions and requires an integrated approach, involving all stakeholders: producers, researchers, public institutions and local communities.

Training to Transform: Education at the Heart of Change

The success of this transition depends on the training of professionals capable of supporting this change. It is crucial to equip engineers, agricultural managers and decision-makers with the necessary skills to understand agroecological and climate issues, with an interdisciplinary approach rooted in the realities on the ground.

Research connected to the living: Observe, Understand, Innovate

Agroecology requires a renewal of research methods. Experimentation must be at the heart of scientific approaches, by promoting natural interactions and rehabilitating the key role of observation in adapting agricultural practices to local specificities.

From Observation to Popularization: Sharing Knowledge as Closely as Possible in the Field

The transmission of agroecological knowledge must be participatory. The farmer-to-farmer approach, supported by visual tools and collaborative platforms, is a powerful lever to encourage the adoption of good practices and build the capacity of producers.

The Farmer, a Central Actor in the Transition

The farmer must not be a simple executor of agroecological policies, but a real driver of change. Its commitment involves increased economic and social recognition, easier access to sustainable financing and better integration into fair trade marketing channels.

Key recommendations

The discussions of the high-level round table made it possible to identify several strategic levers to accelerate the agroecological transition. These recommendations aim to strengthen public policies, encourage innovation and ensure an inclusive and sustainable transition.

1. Integrating agroecology into public policies

- Rethinking agricultural strategies to promote agroecological practices.
- Implement appropriate tax and regulatory incentives.
- Promote the legal and institutional recognition of agroecological systems.

2. Strengthening training and knowledge transmission

- Develop specialized training programs in agroecology.
- Encourage the "farmer-to-farmer" approach and collaborative knowledge-sharing platforms.

- Integrate the principles of agroecology into school and university curricula.
3. **Removing economic and political obstacles**
 - Regulate agribusiness to avoid excessive concentration of resources.
 - Develop innovative financial mechanisms such as carbon finance and biodiversity certifications.
 - Support access to credit and financing adapted to agroecological farms.
 4. **Supporting local markets and family farming**
 - Encourage short supply chains and develop public procurement policies in favour of agroecological products.
 - Protect farmers from price volatility by ensuring stable market opportunities.
 - Promote agroecological products through recognized labels and certifications.
 5. **Ensuring equitable access to land**
 - Adapt land policies to encourage the installation of young farmers.
 - Strengthen the recognition of collective and customary land management methods.
 6. **Raising awareness and involving young people**
 - Adapt the communication on agroecology to make it more attractive.
 - Integrate agroecological modules into educational curricula.
 - Encourage youth entrepreneurship in sustainable agriculture.
 7. **Promoting innovation and transdisciplinary research**
 - Adopt a transversal approach to research, combining traditional knowledge and technical innovations.
 - Develop integrated and collaborative research programs, involving farmers, researchers and other industry stakeholders, to strengthen the understanding of natural interactions.
 - Make experimentation a pillar of the approach, reintroducing the complexity of living things and developing a sense of observation to better understand natural dynamics.
 8. **Strengthening the role of public procurement**
 - Integrate agroecological criteria into public tenders.
 - Directing purchasing policies towards products from sustainable agriculture.
 9. **Creating international synergies**
 - Collaborate with global initiatives to strengthen the recognition and adoption of agroecology.
 - Promote exchanges between countries and good practices adapted to different contexts.
 10. **Valuing the farmer as a central actor of change**
 - Involve farmers in the design of agroecological policies and projects.
 - Support their transition through funding and social recognition schemes.
 - Ensuring fair economic circuits to strengthen their resilience and autonomy.

All of these recommendations constitute a roadmap for a gradual and inclusive agroecological transition, guaranteeing the sustainability of agricultural systems in the face of environmental and social challenges.

The session concluded with the words "Training, structuring and convincing: a transition to be consolidated".

Photo 3: The High-Level Panel, online intervention by Mr. Bruno Romagny

2.6 Session 1: Integrating Agroecology, Policy and Education to Strengthen Climate Change Adaptation: National and Regional Perspectives

Summary of Discussions and Highlights

The first session was dedicated to the integration of agroecology, public policies and education to strengthen climate change adaptation in North Africa.

Mr. Elyes Hamza opened and chaired this session, highlighting the impact of the studies carried out on agroecology in the region.

Mrs. Mélanie Requier-Desjardins (CIHEAM-IAMM, NATAE project) presented a study on the agroecological transition in North Africa conducted within the framework of the NATAE project and which consists of the examination of 25 sectoral national strategy documents, mostly in the agricultural and environmental sectors. Her presentation highlighted a limited recognition of agroecology and a large disparity between national policies. The analysis reveals that agroecology is often reduced to notions such as biodiversity or the sustainable management of natural resources and remains mainly integrated into environmental strategies through international cooperation projects. Agricultural policies are more focused on food security, productivity and competitiveness,

favouring technological and economic approaches to the detriment of agroecology. On the other hand, climate strategies integrate sustainable resource management and renewable energies more broadly.

She concluded by noting that while the concepts of green growth and sustainable economy are mentioned, their implementation varies by country. Clarification of concepts and concrete measures are essential to accelerate the agroecological transition.

Then, **Mr. Mehdi Ben Mimoun (INAT, NATAE project)** presented a study on the integration of agroecology in the educational curricula of four North African countries (Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia) developed in the framework of the NATAE project. The objective of this project is to support the agroecological transition by adapting education systems. The results show an uneven coverage of agroecological principles: some, such as diversity and resilience, are well integrated, while others, such as the circular economy and governance, remain underrepresented. Training provision is fragmented, often limited to regional initiatives and lacks national coordination. In summary, while the biophysical principles of agroecology appear to be partially covered in the context of the university courses inventoried, those of a more social and organizational nature are very often absent from the training courses offered.

Key messages:

- Agricultural **strategies** mainly focus on productivity, competitiveness and export, while paying little attention to agroecology.
- **Perception of agroecology:** The various actors (farmers, researchers, NGOs, public authorities) do not recognize agroecology, which is often perceived mainly in relation to biodiversity and the management of natural resources.
- **Limitations:** Dependence on chemical inputs in the face of droughts and the high cost of organic farming limit the adoption of agroecology.
- **Diversity of strategies:** Great heterogeneity of agricultural and climate policies between countries, with a focus on food security and water management.
- **Green growth and sustainable economy:** These concepts are mentioned, but their implementation varies from country to country, highlighting a need for clarification.
- **Training in agroecology:** Fragmentation of the training offer, lack of national coordination and insufficient integration of the social and organisational principles of agroecology
- **Common challenges:** Fragmentation of training and lack of interdisciplinarity between sectors (governance, economy, social resilience).

Key recommendations:

- Strengthening collaborations between universities, NGOs and international initiatives.
- Integrate more practical and participatory training.
- Cover the underrepresented key principles of agroecology.
- Promote field schools and interdisciplinary training.
- Organize workshops to deepen these issues and explore more effective pedagogical approaches

Link to the presentations can be found [HERE](#).

Photo 4: Presentation of the first results of NATAE on public policies to the participants

2.7 Group work session

The group work was organized with the aim of answering an essential question: “What agroecology do we want to promote and what are the most strategic means to do so?”

Link to the presentations can be found [HERE](#).

The group work was divided into two axes with reference to the elements from the NATAE presentations: one on public policies and communication strategies was led by Ms. Mélanie Requier-Desjardins (CIHEAM-IAMM, NATAE project) and Ms. Rita Jalkh (CIHEAM-IAMM, NATAE project); the second on training and education strategies was led by Mr. Mehdi Ben Mimoun (INAT, NATAE project) and Mr. Youssef Trifa (INAT, NATAE project)

The discussions were therefore organized in each group to successively address two major themes, each illuminated by two specific questions. These points to be developed in the discussions focused on the following elements.

Thematic group 1: *Public policy and agroecology Nexus*

- **Agroecology and food security, transition costs and financing:**
 - How can agroecology and agricultural productivity be reconciled?
 - What are the costs of the agroecological transition and what are the potential ways of financing the transition?
- **What information on agroecology, what recognition of agroecological products on the market?**
 - What information should be promoted on agroecology?
 - What recognition of agroecological products in the sectors and on the markets?

Thematic group 2: *Educating and training in agroecology, challenges and perspectives*

- **Teaching agroecology: an interdisciplinary and systemic approach:**
 - Teaching of Agroecology or Agroecology in all courses?
 - Opening up the bastion of agricultural schools to sociological and economic sciences...
- **Agroecology training between public extension and online training**
 - Vocational training: the role of the public sector and civil society
 - Online training: Opportunities and risks.

The synthesis of the working groups is presented at the end of this report, under the session of the key recommendations from the conference, a multi-stakeholder perspective.

Photo 5: Group work on education and training in agroecology, led by Mehdi Ben Mimoun and Youssef Trifa (INAT, NATAE project)

2.8 Session 2: Agroecology at the international level

Summary of Discussions and Highlights

This session highlighted the essential role of agroecology in the transformation of food systems on an international scale. It highlighted the importance of policy and institutional frameworks for the implementation of agroecological practices, while highlighting their contribution to environmental sustainability and community resilience to climate and socio-economic crises.

The panel, moderated by **Mr. Mohamédou BABA SY**, Director of the **WATER Department of the OSS**, is made up of **Mr. Hédi CHEBILI**, Director General of the **DGQEV-Tunisia**, **Mr. Aymen FRIJA**, Director of **ICARDA-Tunisia**, **Mrs. Zohra LILI**, Director of **IRESA**.

The introductory presentation was made online by **Mr. Dario POLLOCINO**, Programme Manager at **IUCN** and partner of the **NATAE** project.

Key messages:

The key messages addressed by the panelists during this session are as follows:

1. Agroecology as a lever for transforming food systems

- Preservation of natural resources and mitigation of environmental impacts.
- Strengthening the resilience of farming communities to climate change.
- Promotion of local practices adapted to socio-economic and ecological realities.

2. International governance frameworks and policy support

- Contribution of global institutions (FAO, UNCCD, UNFCCC, CBD) to the development of policies favourable to agroecology.
- Integration of agroecology into national strategies in alignment with international commitments.
- Development of regional policy frameworks to support the agroecological transition.

3. Strengthening partnerships and institutional frameworks

- The need to strengthen cooperation between governments, international organizations, NGOs, the private sector and local communities.
- Establishment of institutional frameworks that promote innovation and the dissemination of good agroecological practices.
- Promotion of inclusive initiatives to ensure the commitment of all actors.

4. Issues and challenges for agroecology on an international scale

- Labelling and recognition of products resulting from agroecological practices to promote their marketing.
- Alignment between academic research and farmers' realities to ensure effective application of agroecological principles.
- Widespread adoption of agroecology as a response to global food and environmental challenges.
- Adoption of appropriate and promising policies that accompany the expansion of agroecology.

In conclusion, agroecology, supported by appropriate policies and effective partnerships, represents an essential way to meet the challenges of climate change and food security. Its development at the international level requires better coordination between actors, an adaptation of institutional frameworks and the implementation of concrete actions to promote a sustainable agroecological transition.

Key recommendations:

The main recommendations resulting from the discussions of this session focus on the following points:

- Strengthen the technical capacities and know-how of key agroecology actors, including local farmers, local authorities and local development actors, to enable them to effectively translate international policies and advances into concrete, relevant action plans adapted to national and local realities.
- Encourage international collaboration in the development of standard indicators to measure the ecological transition initiated at the national level in the countries.
- Involve the local stakeholders concerned (practitioners, local farmers, development agents, etc.) in the development of international policies in order to ensure better consideration of the realities on the ground and the specificities of agroecology applied to local contexts.

Link to the presentations can be found [HERE](#).

Photo 6: Ms. Zohra Lili (Director of IRESA) presents a status report on the integration of agroecology in Tunisian training and research structures

2.9 Session 3: Going Further: Linking Agroecology to Food Systems

Summary of Discussions and Highlights

Facilitated by **Ms. Elen Lemaitre-Curri**, Deputy Director of the CIHEAM-IAMM and the NATAE project, this session explored the deepening of the agroecological transition by integrating agroecology into the entire food system. The objective was to go beyond the agricultural dimension to address all links in the food chain, from production to consumption. The discussions shed light on the major challenges related to malnutrition, public health and environmental impacts, while identifying the solutions that agroecology can provide to create sustainable and resilient food systems.

1. **Growing demand for agroecological products:** **Mr. George Viontzos (UTH, Greece, NATAE project)** presented an analysis of consumer expectations in North Africa. He highlighted that environmental awareness is a key driver of demand for agroecological products, but significant disparities exist according to income, age and consumer education.
2. **Inequalities in access to agroecological initiatives:** **Mr. Fatah Ameer (CREAD Algeria, NATAE project)** addressed the situation in Algeria, where agroecological initiatives are

concentrated in high-income areas, limiting the access of vulnerable populations to these products, despite a growing interest in local and natural products.

3. **Importance of short supply chains for sustainability:** **Mr. Olivier Lepiller (CIRAD, France)** presented the MAHDIA project, which works for the convergence between agroecology, water resilience and food security. The project demonstrates how short supply chains and local products can strengthen sustainable food systems, while directly involving producers and consumers in the process.
4. **Sustainable urban agriculture as a lever:** **Mr. Jesper Wohler (Director at Humana People to People, Switzerland)** highlighted the benefits of urban agriculture in promoting a sustainable food model, by setting up green spaces in urban and peri-urban areas. This model aligns with the objectives of the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork strategy.
5. **Priority Actions for the Large-Scale Agroecological Transition in Tunisia:** **Mr. Amine Ben Abdallah (RTTA network, Tunisia)** highlighted the 10 priority actions for the large-scale agroecological transition in Tunisia, aimed at responding to the country's agricultural and environmental challenges. These include training farmers in cutting-edge agroecological practices, setting up reference farms to demonstrate their effectiveness, and introducing financial incentives based on the regenerative performance of soils. Adapting the legal framework, in particular to regulate grazing, liberalize farmers' seeds and promote short supply chains, has also been highlighted as one of the key levers. Finally, a national awareness campaign and the development of a roadmap in consultation with all stakeholders are essential to structure this transition and ensure its long-term success.

Key messages:

1. **Education as a catalyst:** The deployment of educational programs on the benefits of agroecology is essential to change the behaviours of consumers and decision-makers. Targeted training of policymakers is also essential to overcome obstacles to the implementation of agroecological practices.
2. **Accessibility of agroecological products:** It is imperative to ensure that agroecological initiatives do not remain confined to high-income areas. Policies must include measures that facilitate access to these products for vulnerable populations, particularly in Algeria and other similar regions.
3. **Promotion of short circuits:** The promotion of short circuits as a lever to guarantee sustainable and fair production should be a priority. These circuits shorten the distances between producers and consumers, thus reducing the ecological footprint and stimulating local economies.
4. **Integration into public policies:** It is essential to integrate agroecology into national food security and sustainable development strategies. This includes adapting agricultural policies and tax incentives to encourage the transition to more sustainable and resilient food systems.

Key recommendations:

1. **Consumer awareness and education:** Deploy information campaigns to promote the benefits of agroecological products. Increased awareness would encourage wider demand and increase the adoption of these products in the region.
2. **Strengthening financing mechanisms and legal frameworks:** Establish accessible financing mechanisms for agroecological initiatives and develop a legal framework conducive to the recognition of local producers as well as market access for smallholders.
3. **Consolidation of partnerships for a rapid agroecological transition:** Structuring multi-stakeholder platforms by strengthening collaboration between producers, researchers, decision-makers and civil society in order to accelerate the agroecological transition.
4. **Support for urban and peri-urban agriculture:** Strengthen cooperation with local authorities to promote urban agriculture and improve the resilience of cities to food challenges.

The session highlighted the importance of agroecology in reforming food and food security systems globally. By going beyond agriculture to embrace the entire food chain, this approach offers a pathway to sustainability, resilience to climate change, and reducing malnutrition. It is imperative to strengthen collaboration between public and private actors, researchers and local communities to accelerate this transition and ensure the sustainability of food systems.

Link to the presentations can be found [HERE](#).

Photo 7: The speakers of the Food Systems Session

2.10 Session 4: Scaling up and mobilizing funding for the promotion of agroecology

Summary of Discussions and Highlights

Under the chairmanship of **Prof. Assane Soumaré of the University of Nouakchott** and the moderation of **Mrs. Khaoula Jaoui of the OSS**, the session was marked by the interventions of **Mrs. Samia Aloui (APIA, Tunisia)**, **Mr. Joel Teyssier (AFD, Tunisia)**, **Dr. Anneke Trux (GIZ, Germany)** and **Mrs. Nihel Bounaim (Crédit Agricole, Morocco)**. Each of them outlined strategies and opportunities to promote agroecological practices through innovative financing approaches, while reaffirming their support for agroecological solutions for sustainable development and enhanced resilience.

It was stressed that this transition involves both challenges in terms of mobilizing investments, but also opportunities to be fully exploited for the implementation of strategies integrating the agroecological dimension.

The session highlighted the challenges of the agroecological transition, insisting on the role of public institutions, financing mechanisms and support for farmers. Several experiences and good practices from Tunisia and Morocco were presented, highlighting the successes and challenges encountered.

A consensus emerged on the need for a clear national strategy, adequate financial support and an ecosystem conducive to agroecology.

Key messages:

1. Role of public institutions and incentive policies

- The APIA (“Agence de Promotion des Investissements Agricoles”) could play a central role in strengthening aid to farmers;
- Implementation of irrigation and composting subsidies (up to 50%);
- Encouragement of organic certifications to promote agroecological products;
- Development of pilot projects to demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of the transition;
- Strengthening partnerships between farmers and producer organizations.

2. Support for farmers and structuring of the agroecological approach

- Systemic and territorial approach adapted to local specificities;
- Training of farmers and development of know-how;
- Implementation of indicators for monitoring environmental, economic and social impact;
- Alignment with food safety objectives.

3. Funding and access to resources

- Increased mobilization of donors to finance agroecology;
- Development of impact proofs to convince funders;
- Creation of technical repositories to support public policies;
- Strengthening the availability of agroecological inputs and equipment.

4. Innovative financing models

- Promotion of self-financing and diversification of agricultural incomes;
- Development of sustainable financing funds and adapted microcredits;
- Revision of chemical fertilizer subsidies in favour of sustainable alternatives;
- Mobilizing climate finance through carbon assessment methodologies.

5. Experiences and good practices to be capitalized on

- **Tunisia:** Alternating wheat and legumes and direct seeding to improve soil fertility.
- **Morocco:**
 - Flexible agricultural credit schemes (loans repayable after 7 years).
 - Participatory labels recognized by the FAO (PGS AE, Participatory Guarantee Systems in Agroecology). Development of a network of rural animators and itinerant demonstrations.
 - Mapping of farmers practicing resilient agriculture.

Key recommendations:

- **Institutional and policy strengthening:** Development and implementation of a national strategy integrating agroecology into agricultural and environmental policies. This approach aims to align regulatory frameworks, ensure consistent governance, and foster a gradual adoption of agroecological practices at the national and local levels.

- **Access to finance:** Diversification of funding sources by combining public, private and international funds. Development of indicators and evidence to demonstrate the effectiveness of agroecological practices and convince donors to invest sustainably in this transition.
- **Financing a global ecosystem:** Adopting a systemic approach including financing rural infrastructure, supporting applied research, facilitating market access and creating incentive mechanisms for actors in the agroecological value chain.
- **Technical support and training:** Capacity building for farmers and institutions through training programs, partnerships with research centres and the structuring of agroecological value chains. Establishment of technical support mechanisms adapted to local needs and mobilization of community relays for effective knowledge transfer.
- **Economic incentives and product valuation:** Promotion of resilient agricultural practices through support mechanisms such as optimizing irrigation, access to ecological certifications, structuring marketing channels and organizing markets to ensure better competitiveness of agroecological products.
- **Risk management and economic sustainability:** Implementation of quick wins to improve the resilience of farms. Optimization of soil management, provision and adoption of organic fertilizers and conservation practices to enhance productivity while minimizing environmental and climate risks.
- **Sharing and enhancement of know-how:** Creation of platforms for exchange and learning networks between farmers to promote traditional know-how and local innovations. Capitalization and dissemination of good practices to promote the large-scale adoption of agroecological solutions adapted to local contexts.

Link to the presentations can be found [HERE](#).

Photo 8: Panelists of the session on financing agroecology

2.11 Siliana Living Lab Cross visit

Organized by INAT under the framework of the NATAE project, on the side-lines of the regional conference, a cross-visit was held from January 22 to 26, 2025 in Tunis, which offered a platform for exchange and collaboration between Living Labs of the project. This cross visit has provided food for thought on the challenges and opportunities of the agroecological transition by promoting the co-construction of knowledge between farmers, researchers, public institutions and civil society organizations that participated. Presented by **Ms Ines Zouari (INAT, NATAE project)**. This session highlighted the key lessons and perspectives from these field exchanges.

The visit to the Living Lab in Siliana, Tunisia, highlighted the specific challenges of cereal plains, such as soil degradation, the impacts of climate change, difficulties in accessing markets and the lack of technical knowledge on agroecological practices. Through participatory workshops, exchanges with local stakeholders and field experiments, participants explored suitable solutions, such as the integration of legumes into cereal systems to improve soil fertility and strengthen the resilience of farms.

This initiative demonstrated the importance of a territorial and collaborative approach, involving all stakeholders to facilitate the large-scale adoption of agroecological practices. By connecting Living Labs in Tunisia, Algeria, and Morocco, these exchanges helped identify transferable success models and enrich policy recommendations. As part of the regional dynamic driven by the Conference on Agroecology, this approach actively contributes to the construction of a sustainable, resilient agriculture adapted to the climatic and socio-economic challenges of the Maghreb.

Link to the presentation can be found [HERE](#).

2.12 Closing of the conference

2.12.1 Summary of recommendations

This session led by **Mélanie Requier-Desjardins (CIHEAM-IAMM, NATAE project)** allowed to recapitulate the main conclusions of the different sessions and group work.

A summary of the recommendations is provided in the box below.

For public policies, this involves:

- Recognizing agroecology as a modern and innovative form of agriculture and not as a set of outdated practices. Participants emphasized the need to change the agricultural model and to think of agroecology as an embodiment of agricultural modernity.
- Recognize the major role of agroecology as a vector of public health
- Make agroecology an integrated and global approach in the field of agricultural and multi-sectoral public policies
- Involve the private sector in the development of agroecology with financial products adapted and accessible to the greatest number
- Recognize in particular:
 - the agroecological transition as a process and not as a rupture and support the financing of this transition by adapted measures:
 - by promoting change and the provision of new means of production
 - by compensating for the risks associated with these changes in economic and climatic contexts marked by uncertainty

- the pioneering role of CSOs in the dissemination of agroecology and in the promotion and improvement of existing practices
- the role of supporting public policies in the agroecological transition and its scaling up
- the local dimension of agroecology and the consideration of its specificities which requires flexible approaches and instruments and adjusting to diverse contexts.
- Recognize that scaling up agroecology is a question of supply (production) as much as access to the consumption of agroecological products and that it is necessary to:
 - Work in parallel on these two components
 - Design measures progressively and simultaneously between the upstream component (production) and the downstream component (production)

Downstream:

- Conduct awareness and education information campaigns within society: consumers, producers, schools and society in general in connection with overall health (of the environment and people)
- Facilitate the establishment of supply chains (short and national) based on (re)cognition (local markets, specialized shops) of product quality, accessible to small producers
- Make quality supply chains accessible to as many people as possible
- Promote public markets (schools, hospitals) in favour of agroecology, its committed producers and its products to:
 - Encourage agroecological production and secure its outlets
 - Promote societal (re)cognition of agroecology
 - Develop education on nutritional quality among children

Upstream:

Validate the shared observation of stability of yields in agroecological production in times of climate crises compared to a drop in yields in conventional: starting from there, how can we encourage change, its conditions and its scaling up?

- Document the risks/needs associated with the transition for farmers in order to define appropriate solutions at the policy level.
 - Supply issues: physical accessibility of non-polluting inputs, accessibility and innovation needs in machinery and specific tools
 - Economic accessibility: move current subsidies on chemical inputs to subsidies on non-polluting and natural inputs, on conventional machinery to equipment that promotes agroecological practices
 - Need for a business plan to demonstrate the profitability of agroecological farms
- Provide new evidence of the productivity of agroecological systems and their contribution to food security, particularly in drought contexts compared to the conventional model. To do this:
 - Develop and strengthen demonstration platforms, such as multi-stakeholder living laboratories by strengthening existing initiatives;
 - Rely on and support reference farms ensuring monitoring and demonstrations on different productions, on different farm sizes and different climatic levels
 - Involve farmers and their organizations, researchers and civil society organizations.
 - Develop impact measurements of the multidimensional benefits (social, environmental and economic) of agroecology

For Research policies, the recommendations focused on the need to:

- Integrate agroecology into national research programs on sustainable agriculture and
 - Encourage the capitalization of the many experiences conducted by CSOs to avoid the loss of knowledge, practices and experiences
 - Integrate and rethink research and its role in this perspective: promote transdisciplinarity (research partnerships, CSOs and farmers)
 - Recognize the role of and encourage research to validate the pilot initiatives of CSOs and agroecology associations:
 - in order to collectively relay and transfer (multi-partner advocacy) the validated results to public policies
 - for a better definition of support and accompaniment measures

For Education and training policies:

- Better integrate agroecology and its multiple dimensions (agronomic, environmental and social) into school and higher education curricula in agronomy
- Develop online training (MOOCs, etc.) based on capitalization and aimed at disseminating agroecological experiences in the region
- Integrate field experiences into theoretical training by relying on the existence of sites that support experimentation and changes towards agroecological transition, such as living labs.
- Organize a systematic inventory and capitalization of training provided within the framework of CSO activities by mobilizing the participation of researchers and students in these activities
- Identify local knowledge, its adaptation, promote the co-construction of knowledge, its transfer and recognition by appropriate public policies:
 - Co-construct new agroecological knowledge based on local knowledge, concrete experiences and scientific knowledge
 - Mobilize accessible and transferable media (video, podcast, etc.) from one region and country to another for the capitalization and exchange of co-constructed knowledge by promoting direct exchanges between farmers
 - Encourage regional networking, particularly on a Mediterranean scale and the sharing of this knowledge through networks such as MEDAE
 - Design training for national and international curricula focused on the co-construction of this agroecological knowledge in its multiple dimensions and by integrating concrete multi-country experiences and multi-regions.

Link to the closing remarks can be found [HERE](#).

2.12.2 Closing

The regional conference on agroecology ended on January 31, 2025 after three days of intense discussions bringing together researchers, decision-makers, representatives of civil society and private sector actors. The discussions highlighted that agroecology is an essential response to the environmental and socio-economic challenges of food systems in North Africa. The diversity of expertise and experiences shared during this event made it possible to explore the levers needed to accelerate the transition to sustainable and inclusive agricultural practices. The closing of the work was marked by the intervention of Mr. Hamadi Habaieb, Secretary of State to the Minister of Agriculture, Water Resources and Fisheries, who recalled the need for an integrated approach to support the agroecological transition. He highlighted the importance of strengthening synergies between research, public policies and local initiatives in order to build more sustainable food systems. He also highlighted the key role of governments in developing regulatory frameworks that promote the adoption of agroecological practices and the development of sustainable sectors. The

commitment of local stakeholders, the promotion of traditional knowledge and the support of farmers were identified as essential levers to ensure the effectiveness of the actions implemented.

Field experience, illustrated by several case studies, demonstrated the diversity of existing agroecological practices and the efforts made to promote their dissemination. Consumer awareness and the evolution of regulatory frameworks appear to be key elements in structuring more resilient and inclusive food systems.

The discussions also stressed the central role of public policies in structuring an agricultural model that respects ecosystems. The integration of agroecology into national strategies, the mobilization of appropriate financing and the strengthening of training and incentive programs are among the priorities identified. The need for a clear institutional framework, promoting coordination between the different actors, was particularly highlighted.

Intersectoral collaborations and synergies between the different actors were highlighted as essential levers to ensure a successful transition. In this dynamic, the creation of exchange platforms and the sharing of local knowledge emerged as strategic axes to strengthen the adoption of agroecological practices. In addition, raising awareness among the general public, particularly through information campaigns and educational actions, emerged as a determining factor in encouraging more responsible consumption and supporting the growth of agroecological products. Thus, these different approaches are intertwined to promote a sustainable and collective transition. This conference marks a key step in laying the foundations for a strengthened regional dynamic in favor of agroecology. The Sahara and Sahel Observatory reaffirms its commitment to play a leading role in this transition, by facilitating regional synergies and supporting concrete initiatives. The challenge now is to transform these exchanges into tangible actions, anchored in a collective and concerted vision, to build sustainable food systems that serve populations.

Photo 9: The conference organizers with Mr. Hamadi Habaieb, Secretary of State to the Minister of Agriculture, Water Resources and Fisheries, Tunisia

Chapter 3

Communication

3. Communication

3.1 Production and distribution of communication materials

As part of the agroecology conference, several printed materials were produced to ensure effective communication with participants. Brochures and flyers in French and English were produced, their content having been proofread and adjusted before printing.

A poster detailing the project activities was also designed and printed to inform participants about the objectives and achievements of the NATAE project.

In addition, badges and name tags have been prepared to identify participants and facilitate exchanges. In addition, personalised canvas bags and USB sticks were distributed to the participants, containing key documents related to the conference.

A specific visual has been created to dress up the event. It was projected at the back of the stage and printed in banner format, hung in the room to ensure better visibility, especially in the taking of photos and videos.

3.2 Logistical organization and event coordination

An event company was hired to handle the logistical and technical aspects of the conference. This mission included the fitting out of the “classroom” configuration, the installation of the necessary equipment, online broadcasting, as well as interpretation services. Working meetings with the technical team made it possible to plan every detail, and a complete installation of the room was carried out the day before the event to ensure the proper functioning of all the technical and logistical devices.

The hotel selected to host the conference provided three distinct spaces: a large plenary room, a VIP room and a room for group work on 31 January 2025. In addition, an exhibition space has been reserved in the hall to present publications, posters and other useful materials during coffee breaks.

3.3 Reception and registration of participants

A team has been set up to welcome and register participants. Each participant received a kit including several OSS communication tools, including an institutional brochure, brochures and flyers of the NATAE project, a personalized canvas bag, a badge and a USB key.

3.4 Digital communication and media coverage

A digital communication plan has been developed to ensure optimal coverage of the event before, during and after the conference. A dedicated team was mobilized to ensure the publication of content on social networks (Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn), including regular posts, articles published on the OSS website and the dissemination of photos representative of the highlights of the conference.

Janvier 2025							Février 2025						
Jan	Feb	Mar	Avr	Mai	Jun	Juin	Jan	Feb	Mar	Avr	Mai	Sam	Dim
30	31	01	02	03	04	05	30	31	01	02	03	04	05
06	07	08	09	10	11	12	06	07	08	09	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
27	28	29	30	31	01	02	27	28	29	30	01	02	03

[Facebook](#)
[X](#)
[LinkedIn](#)

An interpreter has been made available to translate the publications and articles written as part of this digital communication strategy.

The conference was also streamed online to allow for remote participation and to expand its audience beyond the attendees in attendance. This initiative facilitated access to the discussions for a wider audience, including experts, researchers and policymakers who were unable to travel. The online broadcast also made it possible to document the interventions and to ensure better visibility of the exchanges, in particular thanks to the replays accessible after the event.

Links to the livestream can be found here for [DAY 1](#), [DAY2](#), and [DAY 3](#).

3.5 Digital communication tools, performance and impact analysis

A dedicated platform for the event has been set up as a resource centre with more than 365 registered participants. This platform provided access to all information related to the event, such as panelists' biographies, the agenda, PowerPoint presentations, as well as videos and photos. The QR code leading to this platform has been widely distributed, including on the back of the badges, which has facilitated quick access to these resources. This initiative promoted the engagement of the participants and allowed for optimal monitoring of the content.

Platform link: <https://www.natae-agroecology.eu/fr/regional-conference-on-agroecology/>

15 posts on social networks (Facebook, X, LinkedIn), with about 20 photos distributed per post.

Titre	Date de publication	Couverture	Mentions Publiées et réactions	Commentaires	Partage
Présentoir de l'agroécologie à l'échelle internationale : cette année à portée de clic...	Jeu 30 janvier 17:34	2.4 K	36	0	8
La conférence sur l'agroécologie en partenariat avec les centres de recherche de l'INRAE...	Jeu 30 janvier 12:53	1.4 K	30	0	3
L'occasion de la Conférence Régionale 'Agroécologie - Science et Politique' organisée...	Jeu 30 janvier 12:23	1.2 K	44	1	3
Focus sur la conférence NATAE 'Agroécologie - Science et Politique' dans le journal d...	Jeu 30 janvier 10:22	338	32	0	4
Day 2 of The Regional Conference on Agroecology Science and Policy, scheduled for 3...	Jeu 30 janvier 08:34	741	28	2	8
Le Ministère de l'Environnement et des Bois est organisé en événement officiel 'Confi...	Mer 29 janvier 19:03	1.1 K	37	1	2
Déroulé de la Conférence Régionale 'Agroécologie - Science et Politique' organisée...	Mer 29 janvier 17:40	1.7 K	38	0	9
Day 1 of The Regional Conference on Agroecology Science and Policy, scheduled for 3...	Mer 29 janvier 16:32	257	35	2	8
Tous le 30 janvier 2025 à Tunis, la 27e session du Comité d'Orientation Stratégique (COS...	Mer 29 janvier 12:51	1.4 K	74	2	3
Rapport 1 - Conférence Régionale sur l'Agroécologie - Science et Politiq...	Mer 29 janvier 16:04	727	26	0	0

3 articles published on the OSS website:

<https://www.oss-online.org/fr/OSSNATAE>
<https://www.oss-online.org/fr/NATAE-Corridor-vert>
<https://www.oss-online.org/fr/OSSNATAE31>

The event gained notoriety through increased views, coverage, content interactions, link clicks, visits, and followers. This visibility made it possible to reach a wide audience. Social media interactions, such as likes, comments, and shares, boosted engagement and expanded the reach of content. Clicks on links revealed a real interest in the event, and the increase in visits showed that attendees were increasingly attracted to the information offered. In addition, the increase in the number of followers has helped to create a community around the event, which guarantees its long-term visibility.

3.6 Media Engagement and Press Relations

Collaborative work with the Ministry of the Environment's communication managers made it possible to mobilize local media and journalists. This action aimed to diversify the communication channels and reach a wider audience. To this end, a press release has been prepared and shared with the parties concerned.

A broadcast on the national television news was organized, with the intervention of the Minister of the Environment, the deputy director of the CIHEAM-IAMM and a technical manager of the OSS. They highlighted the challenges of the conference and the role of the NATAE project. This passage was then relayed on social networks to increase its reach.

Link to the podcast video:

https://www.facebook.com/OSSCommunity/videos/1289051382378788?locale=fr_FR

A summary article was written after the conference, recalling its context, the main topics discussed and the recommendations resulting from the exchanges. This article was accompanied by a retrospective video showcasing the highlights of the event. The link to the summary article can be found in [ENGLISH](#) and in [FRENCH](#), and the link to the video can be found at:

[NATAE \(1\).mp4](#)

Chapter 4

Summary and perspectives

4. Summary and Outlook

4.1 Summary and perspectives

The regional conference on agroecology highlighted the importance of recognising this approach as a modern and innovative form of agriculture, rather than just a return to traditional practices. Far from being a sudden break, the agroecological transition must be seen as a gradual process requiring structured support at several levels. Its integration into public policies should not be limited to the agricultural sector alone, but should be extended to other areas to ensure a coherent multisectoral approach. To successfully scale up, it is essential to involve key actors, including the private sector, civil society organizations (CSOs) and public institutions. The challenge lies as much in the supply, in terms of production, as on the accessibility of agroecological products for consumers.

The adoption of agroecology on a large scale requires a strong commitment from the public authorities, in particular through incentive policies and appropriate financing. It is essential to raise awareness among society as a whole – producers, consumers, schoolchildren – of the environmental and health benefits of this transition. This requires information and education campaigns, but also the establishment of more direct and fairer distribution channels. The development of dedicated public markets, particularly for school canteens and hospitals, would encourage agroecological production while securing its outlets. In this dynamic, it is also fundamental to take into account the issue of accessibility to agroecological products, by working simultaneously on supply and demand in order to ensure a viable balance.

In terms of research, it is imperative to provide tangible evidence of the productivity of agroecological systems, highlighting their resilience to climate crises and their contribution to food security. The establishment of demonstration platforms, such as reference farms in different sizes and climatic conditions, would facilitate the dissemination of practices and the assessment of their impact. Research must also reinvent itself by adopting a transdisciplinary approach, involving farmers, researchers and civil society organizations, in order to integrate local knowledge with scientific advances. By validating and relaying the pilot initiatives put in place by the actors in the field, it will be possible to influence public policies more effectively and to better adapt the accompanying measures.

The shift to more sustainable agriculture also implies increased support for agroecological production. One of the main challenges is the availability and accessibility of clean inputs, as well as the need for innovation in machinery and specific tools. A readjustment of agricultural subsidies is necessary: support for chemical inputs and conventional equipment should be reduced in order to redirect this financing towards agroecological solutions. In addition, the profitability of agroecological farms must be demonstrated through solid business models, encouraging more farmers to take the plunge.

Finally, education and the transmission of knowledge are essential levers to ensure the sustainability of the agroecological movement. The integration of this approach into school and university curricula, by highlighting its agronomic, environmental and social dimensions, is a necessity. The co-construction of knowledge, based on the alliance between local knowledge and scientific research, must be encouraged and supported by capitalization and sharing tools accessible to all. The use of appropriate media, such as videos and podcasts, would promote the dissemination of practices and the strengthening of direct exchanges between farmers. The networking of actors at regional level, particularly in the Mediterranean, would contribute to a better circulation of experiences and the adoption of common strategies.

Overall, these recommendations aim to structure an efficient and sustainable agroecological transition, by mobilizing all stakeholders to build a more resilient, inclusive and ecosystem-friendly agricultural model.

Appendices

Appendices

Appendix A. List of Panelists

LIST OF PANELISTS

Name/Surname	Institution	Position Held
Mr. Nabil Ben Khatra	OSS	Executive Secretary
Ms. Elen Lemaitre Curri	CIHEAM-IAMM	Assistant Director
H.E. Mr. Giuseppe Perrone	European Union (EU), Tunisia	Ambassador
H.E. Mr. Habib Abid	Ministry of Environment, Tunisia	Minister
Ms. Mélanie Requier Desjardins	CIHEAM-IAMM	Expert
Mr. Patrice Burger	CURRY	President
Ms. Zohra Lili	IRESA	Chairwoman
Mr. Thierry Dupeuble	IAMM	Director
Mr. Assane Soumaré	University of Nouakchott, Mauritania	Former Minister
Mr. Said Amri	ENAM, Morocco	Director
Ms. Laura Tabet	Nawaya, Egypt	Headmistress
Mr. Elyes Hamza	SPA/RAC, Tunisia	Director, former Minister of Agriculture
Mr. Mehdi Ben Mimoun	INAT	Researcher

Name/Surname	Institution	Position Held
Mr. Hédi Chebili	DGQEV	Managing director
Mr. Aymen Frija	ICARDA-Tunisia	Director
Mr. Georges Vlontzos	UTH	Teacher
Mr. Fateh Ameur	CREAD	Researcher
Mr. Jesper Wohlert	Humana People to People	Director
Ms. Jalila Elati	INNTA	Professor
Mr. Abdelaziz Bouhajba	AAD	Director
Mr. Amine Ben Abdallah	RTTA	Researcher
Ms. Inji Doggui	APIA	Executive Director
Mr. Aimable Twagirayez	PAFO	Representative
Mr. Abdelbacet Hamrouni	ACDD	Responsible
Mr. Joël Teyssier	AFD, North Africa Office	Head of Division
AICS		Headmistress
Mrs. Céline Moyroud	UNDP, Tunisia	Representative
Ms. Nihal Bounaim	Agricultural credit	Project Manager
Ms Mélanie Requier	CIHEAM-IAMM	Professor
H.E. Mr. Azeddine Ben Cheikh	MAHRP	Minister

Appendix B. List of Participants

ON-SITE PARTICIPANTS ATTENDANCE LIST

Name/Surname	Institution	Position Held
Requer Mélanie	NATAE Scientific Coordinator / CIHEAM IAMM	France
Elen Lemaitre Curri	CIHEAM	France
Bruno Romagny	Research Director at the IRD	France
Rita Jalkh	Project Manager and Postdoctoral researcher/IAMM	France
Thierry Dupeuble	Director CIHEAM IAMM	France
Amélie Bourceret	CIHEAM IAMM	France
Fatah Ameur	Research Centre for Applied Economics for Development	Algeria
Souad ben Moussa	Facilitator LL Laghouat Algeria	Algeria
Laura Tabet	Founder of Nawaya NGO	Egypt
Georges Vlontzos	Professor at University of Thessaly	Greece
Ghizlane Echchgadda	Coordinator of the research team "AGREE	Morocco
Mehdi ben Mimoun	Professor INAT	Tunisia
Jesper Wohlert	Humana People to people	Spain
Assane SOUMARE	University of Nouakchott	Mauritania

Raafat MISAK	Professor Emeritus, Desert Research Centre (DRC), Member of the Scientific and Technological Committee	Egypt
Jean Luc CHOTTE	Research Director at the French Research Institute for Development (IRD)	France
Dorothy AMWATA	University Professor	Kenya
Anneke TRUX	GIZ Programme Manager	Germany
Alhamandou DORSOUMA	Acting Director and Head of Division, Climate Change and Green Growth Department at the AfDB	Chad
Jean Luc GNACADJA	Former President of the COS, Former Executive Secretary of the UNCCD Former Minister of Environment and Sustainable Development	Benin
M'hamed Tifouri	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	Algeria
Loucif Seiad Mohamed	Deputy Director Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research	Algeria
H.E. Mr. Diego Mellado	Ambassador of the EU to Algeria	Algeria
Hala YOUSRY	Professor of rural sociology, the Desert Research	Egypt
Samy Al Said Abo Ragab	DRC	Egypt
Khaled Abu Zeid	CEDARE	Egypt
H.E. Ms. Angelina Eichhorst	EU Ambassador Egypt	Egypt
H.E.Mr. Joaquin TASSO VILALLONGA	EU Ambassador Mauritania	Mauritania
Mohammed-Yahya O. LAFDAL	CSE	Mauritania
Patrice Burger	President of CARI	France

Rasheed .H. Alfiteesi	Technical Advisor Ministry of Water Resources	Lybia
H.E. Mr. Ibrahim Al-Arabi Mounir	Minister of the Environment, Libya	Lybia
Amiri Said	Director-National School of Agriculture of Meknes	Morocco
Fatima Zahra El Miri	National IHYAE Program Coordinator (TREEA)	Morocco
Khaled CHERKI		Morocco
H.E. MS. Patricia Llombart Cussac	EU Morocco Ambassador	Morocco
Nihal Bounaim	Crédit Agricole Maroc	Morocco
Farah BOUQARTACHA		Morocco
Mr. Abderrahim Houmy	Director General, National Agency for Water and Forests	Morocco
Aimable TWAGIRAYEZU	PAFO	Rwanda
We are waiting for a name	AICS	Tunisia
El Moeataz ABADI	MRU	Spain
H.E.Guiejeppe Peronne	Ambassador of the EU Tunisia	Tunisia
Matthias Giegerich	GIZ Tunisia	Tunisia
Alexandre Arrobbio	World Bank	Tunisia
Mohamed Amrani	FAO	Tunisia
Malinne Blomberg	BAD	Tunisia
Joël TEYSSIER	AFD	Tunisia
Jamel JRIJER	WWF	Tunisia
Céline MOYROUD	UNDP	Tunisia

Jalila El Ati	Professor	Tunisia
Ezzeddine CHALGHAF	OEP	Tunisia
Mohamed Nawfel BEN HAHA	DGF	Tunisia
Mosbah ABAZA	DGDD	Tunisia
Zouhair NASR	DGINGREF	Tunisia
Aissa Hlaimi	DGRE	Tunisia
DG	AVFA	Tunisia
Najari Sghaier	IRA Mednine	Tunisia
Ghazi Krida	Director INAT	Tunisia
Hedi CHEBILI	DGEQV	Tunisia
Audrey Naulleau	CIRAD	Tunisia
Abdelbacet Hamrouni	ACDD	Tunisia
H.E.Ms. Anne GUEGUEN	Ambassador France to Tunisia	Tunisia
H.E.Mr. François DUMONT	Ambassador Belgium Tunisia	Tunisia
H.E.Mr. Alessandro Prunas	Ambassador Italy Tunisia	Tunisia
H.E. Mr. Josef Philipp RENGGLI	Ambassador Switzerland Tunisia	Tunisia
H.E. Ms.Elisabeth WOLBERS	Ambassador Germany Tunisia	Tunisia
H.E.Mr. Mohammed IBOUMRATEN	Ambassador Morocco Tunisia	Tunisia
H.E. Mr. Mustapha Mohamed Gdara	Ambassador Libya to Tunisia	Tunisia
H.E. Mr. Bassem Yahia Hassan	Ambassador Egypt Tunisia	Tunisia
H.E.M. Azzouz BAALLAL	Ambassador Algeria Tunisia	Tunisia

H.E.M.Sidi Ali Ould Sidi Ali	Ambassador Mauritania Tunisia	Tunisia
Chamseddine Harrabi	DGACTA	Tunisia
H.E Mr. Habib Abid	Minister of the Environment Tunisia	Tunisia
Mr. Elyes Hamza	RAC/SPA	Tunisia
Amin Ben Abdallah	Member/ Tunisian Network for Agroecological Transition	Tunisia
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Aziz Bouhajba	President of the Association for Sustainable Agriculture	Tunisia
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H.E. Mr. Azeddine Ben Cheikh	Minister of Agriculture and Water Resources, Tunisia	Tunisia
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Mokhtar Mahouachi	Professor /ESA Kef	Tunisia
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Zohra Lili Chabaane	IRESA	Tunisia
Haifa Benmoussa	National Agronomic Institute of Tunisia	Tunisia
Youssef Trifa	INAT	Tunisia
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Mokhtar BARAKET	INRGREF	Tunisia
Wafa koussani	Inat	Tunisia
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Hannachi Mohamed ali	National Institute of Field Crops	Tunisia
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Amal BEJAOU	National School of Engineers of Tunis	Tunisia
Samah Ben Chaaban	Regional Agricultural Research Centre Degache	Tunisia
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Sfayhi Dorra	INRAT	Tunisia
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Mohamed Rajhi	Tunisian Space Association TUNSA	Tunisia
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Carpentier Irène	Cirad icarda	Tunisia
Abdallah SINAOU	ALICAP	Tunisia
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Mouna MHAFDHI	Ministry of Agriculture	Tunisia
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Inès Sedraoui	INAT	Tunisia
Mouna Ayachi	Olive Institute	Tunisia
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Khouloud TRABELSI	Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources and Fisheries	Tunisia

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Jamel BENREBAH	IRESA	Tunisia
Hana Guirat	National Agronomic Institute of Tunisia	Tunisia
Ilhem Ben Mansour	Combination of Oasis Shapes and Colours	Tunisia

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Ferjani Elyes	National Agronomic Institute of Tunis	Tunisia
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Ons Baklouti		Tunisia
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Amel kerkeni	Esa mograne Tunisia	Tunisia
Mahdhi Naceur	Institute of Arid Regions of Medenine	Tunisia
Amal noumi	Isacm	Tunisia
NABIL	RIAM	MOROCCO
Amal kamel	ISACM	Tunisia
Molka Jelassi	University of Tunis El Manar	Tunisia
Hichem ben khalifa	Ntr	Tunisia
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Slim Arfaoui	National Institute of Field Crops (I.N.G.C)	Tunisia
Haifa yousfi	Apia	Tunisia
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Mariette de Villiers	University of Pretoria	South Africa
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MSELLEK Wissal	Faculty of Discipline of Larache/ CIRAD Montpellier	Morocco
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ALAMI SOPHIA	CIRAD	Netherlands
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Semia Gharbi	AEFEG	Morocco
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Giulia Giordano	Agroecology Coalition	Italy

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Bakary COULIBALY	DoniLab	Mali
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Ouattara Massadé Abdou-Rahamane Souleymane	No	Ivory Coast
NOUFE Francis	Ministry of Agriculture, Animal and Fisheries Resources of Burkina Faso	Burkina Faso
Moustapha Ibrahim Moussa	Association Against Climate Change and Food Insecurity in Niger "ACCIAN".	Niger
Takwa mezghi	Institut supérieur agronomique chatt mariem	Tunisia
NACANABO Yam-Biga Kévin Sini	Thomas SANKARA University	Burkina Faso
HEBRI SANDA	University of Yaoundé 1	Cameroon
HINDSON	Mesopartner	France
Hossem SAHRAOUI	Biotechnology Research Centre	France
Oyeoussi Charles Balogoun	Africa Esperance NGO	Benin
Jeis DONGO	Hope Land Congo	Democratic Republic of Congo
Aljia Ben Smida	Tunisian Association of Energy, Water and Environment AT3E	Tunisia
Salahdine Skounti	USMS	Morocco
NZAHOU	Marien N'GOUABI University	Congo Brazzaville
Zeddour Mohamed Brahim	University of Tlemcen	France
Zidi Dhouha	INAT	Tunisia

Shili Touzi Ines	Istom engineering school	France
Susan	Tsps	Tunisia
Maeva Borin-Christophe	Microfarm Les Feijoas	France
Anna Maria Geluk	Porticus	Based in the Netherlands
Bishal Kc	Banaras Hindu University	Nepal
Prakriti Ghimire	IAAS	Nepal
Mbacke seck diouf	Entrepreneur	Senegal
Tala KHRAIS	Forum of federations	Jordan
Yves CAPO-CHICHI	Triassic	Burkina Faso
Ifra Mamoudou Diamcoumba	Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Monastir	Mauritania
Abdellatif BOUTAGAYOUT	Moulay Ismail University	Morocco
Khadimou Rassoullilahi DIAW		Senegal
Hayfa kriden	Ecoval Conseil	Tunisia
KOFFI DANIEL	Independent	France
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SOUGUIR SALAHEDDINE	CTAB	Tunisia
Sawsen Meskini		Tunisia
Amy diene		Senegal
Nicossa Paulemont	Konbit Peyizan Grandans (KPGA)	Haiti
Haroun Mamoud Idriss	Solidaridad West Africa	Chad

BALDÉ	Ibrahima	Senegal
Amira Hashanah	INRA Tunisia	Tunisia
Massamba Diop	Mohammed VI Polytechnic University	Morocco
Anslet FRANÇOIS	FOHDD	Haiti
Amir Souissi	AAFC	CANADA
ALBOUCHI	University of Carthage Higher School of Agriculture of Mograne	Tunisia
Wiem Haouari	Soilhence	Tunisia
The Meur	CIRAD	France
Hassane Bil-Assanou ISSOUFOU	Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University of Maradi	Niger
Siwar ibn ghozzi	Ciheam	France
VISENÉ Jean Bethlem	Ms Butchery	Haiti
HIEN Ery Marilynne Christina	Swiss Centre for Scientific Research of Côte d'Ivoire	Ivory Coast
Dario Pollicino	IUCN	Spain
Orsolya Nyàrai	IUCN	Switzerland
Siham Aouzal	Faculty of Sciences of Rabat	Morocco
Ben Abdallah	National Agronomic Institute of Tunis	Tunis
Ismaël PARE	IRPAD/Africa	Burkina Faso
Synda Boulahia Kheder	INAT	Tunisia
OMOMBO MULAMBA Toussaint Josaphat	Official University of Bukavu	Democratic Republic of Congo
Mamane Abdou Issoufou	Abdou Moumouni University	Niger

Siri Abou Dramane	Master's student in genetics	Burkina Faso
Ceus Mario	MAENS	Haiti
Feten Aissaoui	Technical Center for Organic Agriculture	Tunisia
Sabrina Khedher	Manouba Regional Agricultural Development Commission	Tunisia
Muhammad Arshad	Agronomic Research Station, Khanewal, Government of Punjab, Pakistan	Pakistan

Appendix C. Concept Note & Agenda

1. Introduction

Agroecology has emerged as a transformative approach to address the planet's most pressing challenges, including environmental degradation, public health, food security, and nutrition. Supported by diverse stakeholders, such as peasant movements, NGOs, and academic communities, agroecology is increasingly recognized as a holistic approach to these interconnected global issues.

Despite this growing international recognition from FAO's 2018 definition to the HLPE's 2019 principles, there remains a gap between high-level advocacy and actionable policies. Governments have yet to make the tangible commitments needed to fully support an agroecological transformation. While agroecology benefits from a solid scientific foundation and numerous real-world examples of its potential, translating these into impactful policy changes remains challenging. International frameworks like the Rio Conventions offer guidelines for sustainable food systems, yet aligning global practices with these principles requires more decisive action.

The scale and interconnected nature of these challenges require a comprehensive, systemic approach. Agroecology provides such a framework, integrating ecological, sociocultural, technological, economic, and political dimensions. Expanding from individual fields to encompass entire food systems, it draws on various scientific disciplines to address challenges from production to consumption, applying ecological principles to regenerate natural cycles, enhance ecosystem services, and foster long-term sustainability. At the core of agroecology is collaboration, where local knowledge and cultural values play essential roles. This approach fosters co-learning among researchers, practitioners, and farmers, allowing knowledge to flow horizontally across the food chain, creating adaptable, resilient solutions to current and future challenges.

The North African region stands at a critical crossroads, where agriculture is confronted with challenges such as aridity, extreme weather, and water scarcity. These issues not only threaten food security but also contribute to nutritional imbalances and the rise of diet-related diseases, posing significant public health risks. With a high dependence on food imports and increasing vulnerability to climate change, the region faces a vulnerable outlook. Agroecology offers promising solutions to enhance resilience in this context. Rooted in centuries of local knowledge, the region's agricultural practices are well-positioned to adapt to and mitigate climatic stresses. Agroecological methods including agroforestry, integrated pest management, and soil conservation are particularly effective, building on the region's rich biodiversity and sustainable land-use traditions. However, widespread adoption of agroecology is hindered by policy, institutional, and knowledge gaps. Despite these barriers, North Africa presents fertile ground for agroecology, as communities remain closely connected to the land, and there is growing recognition of the need for sustainable practices that ensure both livelihoods and ecosystem health for future generations.

The NATAE project seeks to overcome existing barriers by bringing together Mediterranean research institutions, international organizations, and NGOs with strong local expertise. By focusing on locally adapted combinations of agroecological practices, the project demonstrates their potential to address food security and environmental challenges in North Africa. Central to this approach are the Living Labs (LLs) and the MEDAE network. The Living Labs engage local communities in testing and applying agroecological practices, ensuring practical relevance and impact. Meanwhile, the MEDAE network facilitates cross-sector collaboration, knowledge sharing, and scaling-up of these solutions throughout the Mediterranean region, ultimately strengthening the project's ability to catalyze sustainable, transformative change.

At a pivotal stage of the project (mid-term), **the Regional Conference on Agroecology: Science and Policies**, scheduled to take place from **29 to 31 January 2025 in Tunis, Tunisia**, presents a critical opportunity for North Africa, offering a high-level platform to advance agroecology as a transformative solution to the region's pressing food security, nutrition and environmental challenges. By bringing together leaders from science, policy, and practice, the conference will lay the groundwork for the development of sustainable, equitable, and resilient food systems. Through collaborative dialogue and action, it seeks to drive tangible progress, ensuring that agroecology becomes a cornerstone of agricultural and environmental policies across North Africa, and charts a path towards a more sustainable and inclusive future.

2. Current challenges facing food systems

Today's food systems face critical challenges that threaten their stability, equity, and long-term sustainability. To meet global food demands while protecting the environment and supporting vulnerable populations, it is essential to address these core issues:

- **Climate change and climate variability:** Regions of Africa and other parts of the world are experiencing an increase in extreme weather events (droughts, floods, etc.), which threaten agricultural productivity and food security.
- **Soil degradation and loss of biodiversity:** Intensive use of chemical inputs, monoculture and other conventional farming practices have led to soil degradation, loss of fertility and a reduction in ecosystem services.
- **Socio-economic inequalities:** Small-scale farmers, women and young people are particularly vulnerable in the current food system, with limited access to natural resources and markets.
- **Nutrition and public health concerns:** The shift from traditional smallholder agriculture to intensive, high-input systems has disrupted diets, leading to nutritional imbalances and an increase in diet-related diseases such as obesity and diabetes. Reduced food diversity and the rise of ultra-processed foods have worsened micronutrient deficiencies and chronic diseases, creating significant public health challenges. Neglecting wild and underutilized foods—such as wild edible plants, which are rich in nutrients—misses valuable, sustainable solutions.

3. Agroecology as a sustainable solution

Agroecology is based on the principles of sustainable management of natural resources and the enhancement of traditional knowledge. It combines ecologically viable practices with modern technological innovations to improve productivity while preserving biodiversity, soil and water.

- **Building resilience:** By diversifying crops and adopting regenerative practices, farmers can better withstand climatic and economic shocks.
- **Reducing chemical inputs:** Agroecology promotes the use of biological and natural methods for pest control and fertilisation, reducing dependence on chemical pesticides and fertilisers.
- **Food sovereignty:** By linking local production to local markets, agroecology helps to empower farmers and ensure equitable access to healthy, nutritious food.
- **Public health benefits:** Agricultural diversification through agroecology improves health by increasing access to nutrient-dense foods, combating malnutrition, and reducing diet-related diseases like obesity and diabetes. By promoting the consumption of locally grown, organic produce and reducing reliance on processed foods, agroecology fosters healthier diets, strengthens community health, and leads to improved well-being and reduced healthcare costs.

4. The Crucial Role of Public Policy and Education in Agroecological Transitions

Public policies play a pivotal role in fostering the transition towards agroecological systems. Despite its numerous advantages, agroecology remains underdeveloped due to insufficient political and financial support. To enable this transition, adopting agricultural policies that promote agroecology requires:

- **A coherent policy framework:** Agricultural policies aligned with environmental and social objectives are needed to promote a transition towards more sustainable food systems.
- **Support for research and innovation:** Science plays a key role in the development of new agroecological practices, as well as in assessing their economic and ecological impacts.
- **Education:** (universities, agronomic schools but also sensibilization for the youngest at school are definitely needed at large scale and throughout the region).
- **Economic incentives:** Subsidies and financial support should be redirected to encourage agro-ecological practices and support farmers in their transition.

These policies can be essential catalysts for the transformation towards agroecological systems. By providing **economic incentives**, integrating agroecology into **national development strategies**, and encouraging the **participation of local stakeholders**, they can help to make agroecology a real solution to today's food and environmental challenges.

5. Objectives of the conference

Objective Hand

The Conference aims to serve as a transformative platform for advancing agroecology as a core solution to North Africa's food security and environmental challenges. It seeks to foster high-level dialogue among leaders in science, policy, and practice to drive agroecological transformation, bridge the gap between international frameworks and local policies, and promote sustainable, inclusive food systems.

Specific Objectives

In line with the objectives of the NATAE project, the conference will:

1. **Facilitate Multi-Stakeholder Collaboration:** Provide a platform for farmers, researchers, policymakers, and civil society to discuss challenges, share insights, and explore opportunities for agroecological transitions in the region.
2. **Support the Agroecological Transition:** Mobilize scientific research and policy support to promote the rapid adoption of sustainable, climate-smart practices that focus on community-based approaches to address regional environmental challenges.
3. **Showcase Real-World Solutions and Best Practices:** Present successful agroecological initiatives and examples from North Africa, demonstrating how locally adapted solutions have achieved significant ecological and socio-economic benefits.
4. **Enhance the Impact of Agroecological Practices through Living Labs and the MEDAE Network:** Support the scaling and adaptation of proven agroecological solutions by promoting practical initiatives such as Living Labs and the MEDAE network, ensuring that successful practices are scaled up, adapted to local contexts, and shared across the region.

6. Expected results:

In line with the overarching goal of fostering a regional transition towards sustainable and resilient agricultural systems, the expected outcomes of this initiative will focus on multi-level engagement across policy, knowledge exchange, and financial mechanisms.

1. **Regional Policy Recommendations for Agroecology:** Formulation of comprehensive regional policy recommendations aimed at mainstreaming agroecology across national agricultural and environmental strategies, with a focus on sustainable development, food security, and resilience to climate change. These recommendations will address not only the agricultural sector but also the broader societal engagement needed for successful adoption.
2. **Strengthening Regional Networks:** Establishment and promotion of a regional network (MEDAE) of experts, decision-makers, researchers, agronomists, educators, and farmers to facilitate knowledge exchange, collaborative research, and the promotion of agroecological practices. This network will work towards bridging gaps between research, policy, and practical applications, with the aim of scaling up agroecology across the region.
3. **Integration of Agroecology in Education and Training:** Initiating the inclusion of agroecology in the curricula of agricultural and environmental programs, ensuring future generations of agronomists, researchers, and policymakers are equipped with the knowledge and skills necessary to support agroecological transition.
4. **Financial Mechanisms for Agroecological Implementation:** Identification and development of sustainable financial mechanisms to support the implementation of agroecological practices, focusing on national and regional investments rather than relying solely on international cooperation. This will involve exploring both public and private sector financing, as well as community-based funding initiatives.

7. Participants

The conference will bring together a wide array of voices ranging from the well-known notable Mediterranean agroecologists' experts:

- Ministers & Officials from ministries of environment, agriculture, health, finance working across sectors to coordinate policies and programs;
- Decision-Makers from government and organization leaders responsible for developing policies that pertain to agroecology;
- High level experts working on Research, practice & policy fields leading researchers, practitioners and professionals in nutrition security, agriculture and food systems to provide perspective & engage in discussion;
- Representatives from the NATAE project consortium, including agroecology research and development institutions and organizations;
- Technicians and farmers among to exchange about agroecology practices and knowledge in the Mediterranean;
- Representatives of international organizations and UN convention executive secretaries, other international trends bodies and sustainable development NGOs;
- Representatives from funding institutions to discuss investment opportunities and financial mechanisms supporting agroecology and sustainable development initiatives.
- Civil society and media to include representatives of civil society organizations, media agencies to ensure accountability and wider circulation of the outcomes.

Day 1 (29th January 2025) Opening of the conference

Time	Activity	Announcer
1:30–2:30 pm	Welcoming participants - Registration	
2:30 –3:00 pm	Opening ceremony	
	Under the high patronage of the Ministry of Environment, the opening remarks by the organizers, OSS and CIHEAM, will highlight the significance of the conference and the crucial role of agroecology in addressing food security and environmental challenges across North African countries.	Mr. Nabil Ben Khadra , Executive Secretary, OSS
		Ms. Elen Lemaitre Curri , Deputy Director, CIHEAM-IAMM
		H.E. Mr. Giuseppe Perrone , EU Ambassador, Tunisia
	H.E. Mr. Habib Abid - Minister of Environment, Tunisia	
3:00-3:30 pm	Conference launch	
	Flesh	Mr. Nabil Ben Khadra , Executive Secretary, OSS
	Presentation of the agenda & the conference objectives	Ms. Mélanie Requier Desjardins , CIHEAM-IAMM
	Introduction : an overview of agroecology in the NATAE region as a hot spot of climate change	Prof. Rachel Bezner Kerr , Cornell University (online)
3:30-4:00 pm	Coffee break	
4:00 – 5:00 pm	Agroecology in Action: Insights from the MEDAE Network	
	Flesh	TBC
	Facilitation	Mr. Mounir Majdoub , ACES
	The MEDAE network (Interactive networking) : A platform to connect policymakers, practitioners, and researchers, focusing on shared strategies for sustainable development and resilience building in the Mediterranean and other African regions	Ms. Marion Comptour , CARI (online)- Ms. Mélanie Requier Desjardins , CIHEAM-IAMM
	Learning from Other Regions and networks: Initiatives, Insights, and Pathways for Connection Exploration of initiatives, experiences, and success stories from other regions and networks, offering valuable insights and practical pathways to foster collaboration, knowledge exchange, and stronger connections for advancing agroecology and sustainable practices.	Mr. Almotaz Abadi , Deputy Secretary General, UFM (tbc) Representative from DyTAES Mr. Aimable TWAGIRAYEZU , PAFO Mr. Abdelbacet Hamrouni , ACDD
5:00-6:30 pm	Side event on Tunisian Green Corridor initiative	All (invited)
7:00-9:00 pm	Cocktail Dinner	All

- **Day 2 (30th January 2025) Kick-off conference sessions**

Time	Activity	Announcer
9:00 – 11:00 am	High-level round table : Policy and public education strategies for accelerating the agroecological transition and promotional strategies at all levels	
	Facilitation	Mr. Patrice Burger , CARI President
	Introduction	Ms. Zohra Lili , IRESA President
	Key approaches to accelerating the agroecological transition by focusing on the	Mr. Thierry Dupeuble , Director of IAMM

	development and implementation of effective policies and promotional strategies.	Prof. Assane Soumare , University of Nouakchott, former Minister, Mauritania Mr. Said Amri , Director of ENAM, Morocco Mrs. Laura Tabet , Nawaya Director, Egypt Mr. Bruno Romagny , Research Director, IRD (online) Mr. Elyes Hamza , Director of (SPA/RAC) -Former Minister of Agriculture, Tunisia
11:30 – 13:30 am (including the coffee break and the discussion)	Session 1: Agroecology, Policy and Education Integration to enhance adaptation to climate change: national and Regional Perspectives	
	Flesh	Mr Elyes Hamza , Director of (SPA/RAC)
	Introduction: Inter-sectoral policy review from an agroecology perspective. Review of curricula on agroecology in 4 North African countries	Ms. Mélanie Requier , CIHEAM-IAMM Mr. Mehdi ben Mimoun , INAT
	Introducing the multi-actor working groups session	INAT for Education & training CIHEAM-IAMM for public policies & agroecology
	4 Working groups session	Public policies & agroecology groups facilitators: Ms Rita Jalkh and Ms Mélanie Requier-Desjardins (CIHEAM-IAMM) Education & training groups facilitators: Mr Youssef Trifa and Mr Mehdi ben Mimoun (INAT)
1:30 – 2:30 pm	Networking lunch	
2:30 – 3:30 pm	Session 2: Agroecology at international scale	
	Facilitation	Mr. Lamine Baba Sy , OSS
	Introduction: Regional and international policies and agroecology	Mr. Dario Pollicino , IUCN (online)
	Panel session: Agroecology in the 3 Rio conventions: Encouraging the development and implementation of policies that integrate agroecology into national and regional strategies	Dr. Hala Yousry , Professor of rural sociology, DRC, Egypt Mr. Khaled Cherki , President of UNCCD African group Negotiator, Morocco Mr. Hédi Chebili , General Director, DGQEV Mr. Aymen FRIJA , Director ICARDA-Tunisia
	Discussions	All
	Session 3 - Going further: linking agroecology with food systems	
	Flesh	Dr. Hela Yousry , DRC
	Facilitation	Ms. Elen Lemaitre-Curri , CIHEAM

3:30 pm – 5:30 pm (including the coffee break and the discussion)	Introduction: Exploratory Analysis of Agroecological Initiatives and the Promotion of Healthy and Sustainable Food	Prof. Georges Vlontzos , UTH Mr. Fateh Aneur , CREAD
	Panel session on Awareness Campaigns: Engaging the Public and Consumers in the Shift Towards Sustainable Farming: Empowering the general public and consumers with knowledge about the vital importance of sustainable farming practices in protecting ecosystems, enhancing food security and public health, and combating climate change.	Mr. Jesper WOHLERT , Director Humana people to people Ms. Jalila Elati , Professor, INNTA Mr. Olivier Lepiller , CIRAD (online)
	Panel on food systems Insights and perspectives from representatives of civil society, local governments, and researchers, focusing on inclusive approaches and collaborative solutions to build sustainable and resilient food systems.	Representatives from civil society and local governments Mr. Abdelaziz Bouhajba , AAD Mr. Amine Ben Abdallah , RTTA

Day 3 (31st January 2025) Summary and avenues for future work & opportunities

Time	Activity	Announcer
09:00– 10:30 am	Session 4: Scaling Up and Mobilizing Funding to Advance Agroecology	
	Flesh	Prof. Assane SOUMARE
	Facilitation	Ms. Khaoula Jaoui , OSS
	Introduction	Ms. Inji Doggui , General Director APIA
	Panel session: Financing Agroecology: A platform to showcase strategies and opportunities for expanding agroecological practices through innovative funding approaches and collaborative efforts, aiming to support sustainable agricultural transitions at scale.	HE.Mr. Giuseppe Perrone , representative of EU Mr. Joel Teyssier , Head of division AFD, North African Office Dr. Anneke Trux , GIZ Ms. Andrea Senatori , Director Aics Ms. Céline Moyroud , representative of UNDP Tunisia Ms. Nihal Bounaim , Crédit Agricole Representatives from: WB, FAO (tbc), AfDB (tbc)
10:30 – 10:50 am	Coffee break	
10:50 – 11:50 am	Session 5: Key Takeaways and Synthesis	
	Flesh	Ms. Mélanie Requier-Desjardins , CIHEAM-IAMM
	Restitution over the working group sessions: (i) Education, (ii) Training, (iii) Public policy, Food Security and Agroecology	Reports: Representatives from OSS & NATAE Consortium

	Synthesis of discussions and key messages, Recap of the conference, summarizing key discussion points with takeaways	
11:50 am – 1:00 pm	Session 6: Closing Insights Strategy and action planning for future collaborations	Ms. Ndeye Fatou Mar, OSS, Director of Land and Biodiversity Department
	Official closing by: Minister of Agriculture, Hydraulic Resources and Fisheries, Tunisia	H.E. Mr. Azeddine Ben Cheikh-MAHRP
1:00 pm	Networking lunch	All

Appendix D. Session Guidance Note

1. Introduction

This guidance note is designed to help panelists prepare for their participation in the Regional Conference on Agroecology: Science and Policy. It provides an overview of each session, details about the themes and introductory presentations, and specific questions to guide your contributions.

The conference aims to:

- Showcase agroecology as a critical approach for climate change, adaptation and mitigation.
- Bridge policy, research, and practice to foster agroecological transitions.
- Facilitate networking among stakeholders from Mediterranean and African regions.

Agroecology in Action: Insights from the MEDAE Network

Date and Time: January 29, 2025, 4:00–5:00 PM

Chair: Mr. Nabil Ben Khatra, OSS

Moderator: Mr. Mounir Majdoub, ACES

Introductory Presentations:

- **Prof. Rachel Bezner Kerr (Cornell University, online, TBC):** Overview of agroecology in the NATAE region as a hotspot for climate change adaptation (10 min).
- **Ms. Mélanie Requier Desjardins/ Ms. Marion Comptour (CARI, online):** Interactive networking on the MEDAE network's role in connecting policymakers, practitioners, and researchers (10 min).

Panelists: 8 min per speaker

- **Mr. Almotaz Abadi (UFM, Deputy Secretary General for Water, Environment, and Blue Economy)**
- **Representative from DyTAES (Senegal, online)**
- **Mr. Aimable TWAGIRAYEZU (PAFO, Rwanda)**
- **Mr. Abdelbacet Hamrouni (ACDD, Tunisia)**

Key Themes and Questions:

1. What are the most impactful agroecological practices implemented in your region, and what lessons can be shared?
2. What barriers exist in connecting policymakers, researchers, and practitioners, and how can these be addressed?
3. How can the MEDAE network foster collaboration to scale agroecological solutions across regions?

High-level round table: Policy and public education strategies for accelerating the agroecological transition and promotional strategies at all levels

Date and Time: January 30, 2025, 9:00–11:00 AM

Moderator: Mr. Patrice Burger, President of CARI

Introductory Presentations:

- **Mrs. Zohra Lili, IRESA:** An overview of the importance of public education policies and strategies for accelerating the ecological transition in North Africa (10 min).

Panelists: 7 min per speaker

- **Mr. Thierry Dupeuble, Director of IAMM**
- **Prof. Assane SOUMARE, University of Nouakchott, former Minister, Mauritania**
- **Mr. Bruno Romagny, Research Director, IRD (online)**
- **Ms. Laura Tabet, Nawayya, Egypt**
- **Mr. Elyes Hamza, Director of Specially Protected Areas Regional Activity Centre (SPA/RAC) -Former Minister of Agriculture, Hydraulic Resources and Fisheries, Tunisia**

Key Themes and Questions:

1. What are the most effective policy actions to accelerate the agroecological transition at different scales?
2. How can public education and communication campaigns drive awareness and adoption of agroecology?
3. How can cross-sectoral collaboration and advocacy efforts enhance the implementation of agroecological strategies?

2. Session details and panelist guidance

Session 1: Agroecology, Policy and Education Integration to enhance adaptation to climate change: national and Regional Perspectives

Date and Time: January 30, 2025, 11:30–13:30 AM

Chair: Mr. Elyes Hamza, (SPA/RAC)

Introductory Presentations:

- **Ms. Mélanie Requier-Desjardins (CIHEAM-IAMM):** Inter-sectoral policy review on agroecology (10 min).
- **Mr. Mehdi Ben Mimoun (INAT):** Analysis of agroecology curricula in North Africa (10 min).

Working Groups:

- **1st WG and 2nd WG : Education and training : INAT, Mr Youssef Trifa and Mr Mehdi ben Mimoun**
 - **1st WG: Education**
 - **2nd WG: Training**
- **3rd WG and 4th WG: Nexus Food security and agroecology, CIHEAM-IAMM, Ms. Rita Jalkh and Ms Mélanie Requier**
 - **agroecology and food security and costs of the transition period**
 - **Information on agroecology and the recognition of agroecological products in markets**

Session 2: Agroecology at the International Scale

Date and Time: January 30, 2025, 2:30–3:30 PM

Facilitator: Ms. Ndeye Fatou Mar, OSS

Introductory Presentations:

- **Dr. Hala Yousry (Desert Research, Egypt):** Agroecology in the context of the 3 Rio Conventions (10 min).
- **Mr. Dario Pollicino (IUCN, online):** Exploring Regional and International Policy Frameworks from an Agroecological Perspective (10 min).

Panelists: 8 min per speaker

- **Dr. Hala Yousry, (DRC), Egypt**
- **Mr. Khaled Cherki, UNCCD African Group Negotiator, Morocco**
- **Mr. Hédi CHIBILI, DGQVE, Tunisia**
- **Mr. Aymen FRIJA, ICARDA-Tunisia, Representative from the NATAE Consortium**

Key Themes and Questions:

1. How can global conventions (e.g., climate, biodiversity, desertification) better support the integration and scaling of agroecological approaches?
2. What are the key challenges in aligning international policies with local agroecological practices?
3. How can international collaboration improve policy coherence and implementation?

Session 3: Going further: linking agroecology with food systems

Date and Time: January 30, 2025, 3:30–5:30 PM

Chair: Dr. Hela Yousry, DRC

Facilitation and short introduction to the topic: Ms. Elen Lemaitre-Curri (CIHEAM-IAMM) (5 min).

Awareness Campaigns: Engaging the Public and Consumers in the Shift Towards Sustainable Farming: Empowering the general public and consumers with knowledge about the vital importance of sustainable farming practices in protecting ecosystems, enhancing food security and public health, and combating climate change.

Introductory Presentations:

- **Prof. Georges Vlontzos (UTH):** Agroecology from the perspective of consumers, first results from consumer surveys in NATAE (10 min)
- **Mr. Fateh Ameur (CREAD):** Exploratory analysis of agroecological initiatives and the promotion of healthy, sustainable food in the wilaya of Algiers (10 min).

Panelists: 8 min per speaker

- **Mr. Jasper Wohlert (Humana People to People)**
- **Ms. Jalila Elati, INNTA**
- **Mr. Olivier Lepiller, CIRAD (online)**
- **Mr. Abdelaziz Bouhajba, AAD**
- **Mr. Amine Ben Abdallah, RTTA**

Key Themes and Questions:

1. How can awareness campaigns engage consumers in supporting sustainable farming?
2. What role do local governments play in integrating agroecology into urban food systems?
3. How can partnerships across sectors strengthen the resilience of food systems?

Session 4: Scaling Up and Mobilizing Funding to Advance Agroecology

Date and Time: January 31, 2025, 09:00 AM–10:30 PM

Facilitation: Ms. Khaoula Jaoui, OSS

Introductory Presentation: (local experience):

- **Ms. Inji Doggui, APIA** (10 min).

Panelists: 8 min per speaker

- **Mr. Stéphane Brossard**, EU
- **Mr. Joel Teyssier**, AFD, North African Office
- **Dr. ANNEKE Trux**, GIZ
- **Ms. Nihal Bounaim**, Crédit Agricole
- **Ms. Andrea Senatori**, Aics
- **Ms. Celine Moyroud**, UNDP Tunisia
- **Representatives from AfDB, FAO, WB**

Key Themes and Questions:

1. What innovative funding mechanisms can support agroecological initiatives?
2. How can financial institutions prioritize agroecology in their portfolios?
3. What metrics should be used to measure the impact of investments in agroecology?

Session 5: Key Takeaways and Synthesis

Date and Time: January 31, 2025, 10:50 AM–11:50 AM

Chair: Ms. Mélanie Requier-Desjardins, CIHEAM-IAMM

Reporters: Restitution over the 4 working group sessions

NATAE

North African Transition
to AgroEcology

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Funded by
the European Union

This project is funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement no. 101084647. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. For the associated partner in the NATAE project, this work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Project funded by

 Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI